

 SCIENCE
COMES TO
TOWN 2027

Bringing Science
Closer to Citizens

Deliverable 1.1 | 5 June 2026

Science4Everyone Inspirational Formats

Irene Lapuente and Joana Macalhães |

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Project short name	Science4everyone
Project long name	Science Comes to Town: Bringing Science Closer to Citizens - Science4Everyone
GA#	101292372
Version Number	1.1
WP Number	1
WP Lead Partner	Science For Change
Date	04/06/2026
Deliverable Number	D1.1
Document Type	Other
Distribution	Public
Summary (if applicable)	-
Contributor(s) / Author(s)	Joana Magalhães, Irene Lapuente
Peer review(s)	-
Revision History	05/06/2026 - APRE

D1.1 – 'Science4Everyone' Inspirational Formats

Index of Contents

1 Introduction	8
2 Handbook structure	9
3 Dissemination	10
3.1 FameLAB	10
3.2 Naukas	10
3.3 Science on the Pouf	11
3.4 ArtScience Street Performance	12
3.5 #ArtScience23: Art and Science Cultural Agenda	12
3.6 Stand-Up Science	13
3.7 #StandUpScience	14
3.8 Transmedia_Lab Mandarinina	14
3.9 Desafíos del Océano: científicas al Mando	15
3.10 MurCIENCIA	16
3.11 Disseminating Science through Theatre	16
3.12 EcoScienceCircus	17
4. Dialogue and engagement	19
4.1 Smog tasting	19
4.2 Pint of Science	19
4.3 Science pairing	20
4.4 Science reading club	21
4.5 Living Libraries	21
4.6 Science BiblioBus	22
4.7 Augmented City: City, culture and science	22
4.8 Urban itinerary	23
4.9 Student-led Multi-platform Bioscience Communication Initiative	24
4.10 Behind the Curtain of Science	24
4.11 Game Cafés	25
4.12 Kaleidoscope Dialogues: Science, Society, and Conversation	26
4.13 Exploring the Microcosm: Foldscope Science Across India	27
4.14 Mind the Lab	27
4.15 Science in the Kitchen	28
4.16 Shake up your curiosity at Science Cocktails	29
4.17 Science ice cream van	30
4.18 Supermarket Sweep: The CoDiet Escape Room	30
4.19 Science Nest	31
4.20 Science SLAM	32

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

4.21 Science Family Day/Open Day	33
4.22 Science Bingo	33
4.23 Science Memory Game	34
4.24 STEMcyclists	34
4.25 SOILSCAPE	35
4.26 Women in Science Quiz	36
4.27 Imagine Science Film Festival	36
4.28 Astronomy Outreach	37
4.29 The Sound of Sciences (SoSTEAM)	38
4.30 Donner Pensant -Tasteful conversations to empower good practices in science	38
4.31 Guerrilla Science	39
4.32 Sports and Science	40
4.33 Science Reading Corner	41
4.34 Mis/disinformation – A discussion game	41
4.35 IUCAmundi: Connecting Research, Territory and Society	42
5. Participatory and Citizen Science	45
5.1 BioBus	45
5.2 Sensetinta Science Fanzine Workshop	45
5.3 GenB Educational board game	46
5.4 Ocean Science Jam	47
5.5 Engihack	48
5.6 MULTI-ENGAGE Hackathon	48
5.7 Seed Library	49
5.8 Citizen Science Day	49
5.9 Un giro di scienza - science cargo bike	50
5.10 Inspiraciència	51
5.11 Community Gardens	51
5.12 Illustraciencia	52
5.13 Researchers-in-Residence	53
5.14 Artist-in-Residence: ARTS AT CERN	54
5.15 Bojos per la Ciència	54
5.20 Science snorkeling	55
5.21 Climate Stories Map (CSM)	55
5.21 Thermo Staat	56
5.22 Poseidon	57
5.23 Soil Sentinel	58
5.24 SENSORBIKES	58

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

5.25 Scientific Area Networks - SANs	59
5.26 European Researchers' Night	60
5.27 SOILTRIBES	60
5.27 FOTCIÈNCIA	61
5.28 GEOVACUI	62
5.29 Picaduras de conocimiento	62
5.30 Pavement Plants	63
5.31 Genigma	64
5.32 Citizen science journalism and Data4CitSciNews exhibition	64
5.33 "Should our medicine go viral?" public tribunal-style debates	66
5.34 EMERGENCE@UPorto – Digital Media Science Communication Hackathon	67
5.35 The Journey: From Venice to Rotterdam	67
5.23 OdourCollect	68
6. Other relevant sources	70

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Contributors

Name	Organisation
Joana Magalhães	Science For Change
Irene Lapuente	Science For Change

Peer Reviews

Name	Organisation
-	-
-	-
-	-
-	-

Revision History

Name	Organisation
Version 1.0	Science For Change
Version 1.1	APRE
-	-
-	-

1 Introduction

Science Comes to Town is a new flagship European initiative to strengthen citizens' trust and engagement in science, funded under the WIDERA Work Programme of Horizon Europe, awarding €6 million to a small group of cities to host a year-long programme of science engagement.

The initiative aims to transform urban spaces into interactive science hubs, enabling citizens to connect with researchers and explore how science impacts daily life. The topic has been included also in Horizon Europe Work Programme 2026-2027 for the editions scheduled to take place in 2027, 2028 and in 2029.

Following the **UNITES** project, Science4Everyone will extend this model into 2027, across four host cities (Aarhus (Denmark), Genova (Italy), Kaunas (Lithuania), and Oeiras (Portugal) in the EU. The programme will include more than 1.400 participatory events and activities over the course of a year and is structured around the five **EU Missions** in Horizon Europe: adaptation to climate change, cancer prevention and care, ocean and water restoration, smart cities, and healthy soils. This means that every activity, from large-scale festivals to citizen science experiments, is an entry point into the research agenda that the European Union has identified as its priority for this decade.

This handbook is intended to inspire the Science Comes to Town annual programme, with innovative activity formats to be implemented by the Science4Everyone project in the four host cities during 2027, but also create a bridge between UNITES and the forthcoming projects, as well as other already existing initiatives such as the European Researchers Night, Researchers at Schools, Science Weeks, Citizen Science Weeks, Science Festivals, or projects such as **COALESCE**, **IMPETUS** and **ECS**, among others.

For this, we gathered inspirational formats to communicate and engage audiences with science, particularly focusing on those which innovate in particular aspects on engaging hardly reached audiences and unconventional venues, how these guarantee the accuracy of the scientific information or how these could be catalysts for policy change. Besides desk-research and contributions from partners, in order to make this process open and encourage participation from a wider science communication community, we created a survey shared via the **European Competence Centre for Science Communication platform**, the **COALESCE Hubs** and other collaborating organisations, whose contributions were hereby included.

Following on the science communication and public engagement, and more extended arts community successful experiences, we invite readers of this handbook to become inspired in formats from the more traditional to the more innovative, find new ideas, contributors and even spur collaborations for future event curation, delivery and/or replicability, towards a more connected ecosystem.

This is not intended to be a closed handbook, but that will grow and be revised in the future.

2 Handbook structure

Overall, the activity formats have been structured under **three main pillars corresponding to three engagement levels: (i) dissemination, (ii) dialogue and engagement, and (iii) participatory and citizen science**. Whilst in this handbook activity formats are listed independently, we encourage readers and potential event organisers to see them as part of an extended programme that considers the coexistence of three levels of engagement (Metcalfe, 2019), and the interconnection between activities, encouraging participants to move into related activities with higher levels of participation.

This may include: **(i) dissemination**, science lectures, conferences, art-science exhibitions, film screenings, etc; **(ii) dialogue and engagement**, science education and capacity building activities, public talks in relaxed settings, sky observations, Lab Open Days, open-mic science nights, games cafés, etc, **(iii) participatory and citizen science** initiatives, hackathons, crowdsourcing activities, etc.

Briefly, each activity describes:

Main objective: including any scientific, learning and/or engagement objectives

Summary: short summary of the activity.

Target groups:

EDU: students, teachers and educators

ACA: researchers

CIV: citizens, families and CSOs

POL: policymakers and research funders

ENT: business and start-ups

UND: underrepresented groups (including migrants, LGBTQIA+, women, disabled, minorities with a focus on inclusivity)

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other):

Cancer

Climate, Adaptation to climate change

Ocean, Restore our Ocean and Waters

Cities, Climate-neutral and smart cities

Soil, A Soil Deal for Europe

Science In Summer

Careers in R&I - with events that promote research and innovation career paths

Other

Venues: may include both traditional and non-formal community spaces - such as botanic gardens, parks, libraries, marketplaces and board game cafés - to broaden access to science and stimulate engagement in everyday environments.

Other categories, such as the **innovation factor**; any reported **impact** on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience; **inclusion and diversity** considerations; and **limitations found**.

In the end of the handbook you will also find several repositories with relevant and award-winning formats that can be consulted at any time.

3 Dissemination

3.1 FameLAB

Title: FameLab

Contributor: British Council

Country of implementation: Launched in the UK

Start date of initiative: 2005

Website: <https://www.youtube.com/user/famelab>

Target group: ACA, POL, ENT

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer, and Careers in R&I

Venues: FameLab events take place in science festivals, universities, theatres, and public venues, with international finals hosted annually at the Cheltenham Science Festival in the UK.

Main objective: The initiative aims to identify, train, and promote young scientists and engineers with strong science communication skills, making science accessible and engaging for the general public.

Summary of initiative: FameLab is an international science communication competition where participants explain scientific concepts in a three-minute presentation evaluated on content, clarity, and charisma, while also receiving communication training and mentoring.

Innovation factor: FameLab introduced an innovative format that combines science communication training with a live competition model, using short, engaging performances to make complex scientific topics accessible and entertaining for broad audiences both in-person and online.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: FameLab has improved participants' communication confidence, storytelling skills, and public engagement abilities, while also increasing public interest and understanding of science through accessible presentations.

GEDI considerations: FameLab promotes inclusion by encouraging participation from young researchers of different genders, nationalities, and scientific disciplines, although access may still depend on language skills, educational background, and institutional support.

Limitations found: N/A

3.2 Naukas

Title: Naukas

Contributor: Naukas

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2013

Website: <https://naukas.com/>

Target group: ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer, and Careers in R&I

Venues: It happens in theatres and science museums.

Main objective: To make science accessible, engaging, and entertaining for broad audiences by bringing researchers and science communicators closer to the public through dynamic talks, live events, and digital content. The initiative aims to promote scientific culture, critical thinking, and appreciation of science in society.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Summary of initiative: Naukas is one of the largest science communication platforms in the Spanish-speaking world, bringing together scientists, educators, journalists, and communicators from diverse disciplines. Through public events, short talks, online articles, videos, and interactive activities, Naukas presents scientific topics in an accessible, rigorous, and entertaining way for audiences of all ages.

Innovation factor: The initiative combines scientific rigor with storytelling, humor, and live performance, transforming science communication into a cultural and entertainment experience. Its short, engaging presentation format and multidisciplinary approach help attract audiences that may not normally attend scientific events, making science more approachable and memorable.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Naukas increases public understanding of scientific topics while fostering curiosity, critical thinking, and evidence-based reasoning. By presenting science as relevant, understandable, and enjoyable, it helps improve attitudes towards research and encourages audiences to engage more actively with scientific issues that affect society.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promotes inclusiveness by covering a wide range of scientific disciplines and societal issues, engaging audiences with different interests and backgrounds. Its open-access events, diverse pool of speakers, and commitment to showcasing different voices in science contribute to broader representation and participation in science communication. Accessibility measures, such as sign language interpretation in some events, further support inclusive engagement.

Limitations found: N/A

3.3 Science on the Pouf

Title: Science on the Pouf

Contributor: Associazione Festival della Scienza

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: <https://www.festivalcienza.it/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Squares, streets, parks

Main objective: Bringing people closer to science with curious subjects.

Summary of initiative: The initiative consists of placing ten large, brightly coloured poufs in a public space, such as a square, street, or park, to create an informal setting for science conversations. Groups of 20–30 citizens gather around a scientist to discuss a specific topic. Sessions are repeated throughout the event, with different scientists and subjects, allowing participants to explore a variety of scientific themes. The success of the format relies on engaging and inspiring speakers who can stimulate dialogue and curiosity among the audience.

Innovation factor: Science on the Pouf innovates science communication by transforming everyday public spaces into informal discussion hubs where citizens can interact directly with scientists in a relaxed and accessible environment, encouraging spontaneous participation, dialogue, and curiosity outside traditional academic settings.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The initiative increases public interest in and understanding of science through informal discussions with researchers. By making science more accessible and engaging, it fosters curiosity, promotes positive attitudes towards research, and encourages citizens to engage with scientific topics relevant to society.

GEDI considerations: The inclusion of a variety of subject areas enhances its alignment with GEDI principles. The diversity of content ensures that different perspectives, interests, and societal dimensions are considered, thereby fostering a more inclusive and comprehensive approach.

Limitations found: N/A

3.4 ArtScience Street Performance

Title: ArtScience Street Performance

Contributor: la Mandarina de Newton | FJMR

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: <https://fundaciojuliomunozramonet.org/agenda/cicle-aigua-water-eau/>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Ocean, Science In Summer

Venues: It can include formal and non-formal community spaces such as science museums, art galleries, parks or streets.

Main objective: To engage the public with scientific concepts through artistic performances that spark curiosity, challenge assumptions, and encourage reflection on complex societal and environmental issues. It aims to make science accessible while fostering critical thinking about the role of science in everyday life.

Summary of initiative: Science and Arts Street Performance combines live artistic expression with scientific ideas in public spaces. Through theatre, music, dance, visual storytelling, and interactive acts, it explores topics such as climate change, biodiversity, technology, and human behaviour, inviting audiences to experience science in unexpected and thought-provoking ways.

Innovation factor: It uses the performing arts as a platform for science engagement, transforming public spaces into arenas for exploration and dialogue. By blending creativity, emotion, and scientific inquiry, it encourages audiences to approach complex topics from new perspectives and question established narratives.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a deeper awareness of scientific issues while developing a more reflective and critical perspective on their implications. The performances can inspire curiosity, stimulate discussion, and encourage audiences to engage more actively with scientific, environmental, and social challenges.

GEDI considerations: It is designed to reach diverse audiences by bringing science directly into accessible public spaces. Through inclusive storytelling and representation of different voices and experiences, it creates opportunities for broad participation and encourages dialogue on science-related issues from multiple cultural, social, and personal perspectives.

Limitations found: N/A

3.5 #ArtScience23: Art and Science Cultural Agenda

Title: #ArtScience23: Art and Science Cultural Agenda

Contributor: la Mandarina de Newton | FJMR

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: <https://fundaciojuliomunozramonet.org/agenda/artscience23/>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Parks and gardens

Main objective: To engage the public in exploring the concept of time through the intersection of art and science, encouraging participants to question how time shapes our understanding of nature, society, memory, and the physical world. It aims to foster curiosity and critical reflection on complex scientific and cultural ideas.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Summary of initiative: #ArtScience23 is a multidisciplinary programme of performances, citizen science activities, workshops, dialogues, documentaries, and artistic interventions that brings together art and science around a common theme: time. Hosted in the gardens of the Julio Muñoz Ramonet Foundation, the initiative invites participants to experience and interpret time as both a scientific phenomenon and a cultural construct.

Innovation factor: It combines artistic creation, scientific inquiry, and public participation in a shared space for experimentation and dialogue. By approaching scientific concepts through sensory, creative, and reflective experiences, it challenges conventional science communication and encourages audiences to engage with uncertainty, complexity, and multiple ways of knowing.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop a richer understanding of scientific concepts related to time, climate, health, mathematics, and natural processes while reflecting on their social and personal dimensions. The programme promotes curiosity, interdisciplinary thinking, and a greater willingness to engage with complex issues that do not have simple answers, fostering a more reflective relationship with science and society.

GEDI considerations: The initiative is designed as an open and accessible public programme that welcomes audiences with diverse backgrounds, interests, and levels of scientific literacy. By combining artistic and scientific perspectives, it creates multiple entry points for participation and values different forms of knowledge, expression, and lived experience.

Limitations found: N/A

3.6 Stand-Up Science

Title: Stand-Up Science

Contributor: Ben Miller

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://www.benmillercomedy.com/copy-of-stand-up-science-1>

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Theatres

Main objective: The main objective of Stand-Up Science is to make science accessible, relatable, and entertaining through comedy. By using humour as an entry point, the project aims to engage audiences with scientific ideas while encouraging curiosity, critical thinking, and reflection on complex topics that often feel intimidating or inaccessible.

Summary of initiative: Stand-Up Science is a live comedy performance created by scientist-turned-comedian Ben Miller that combines stand-up comedy with scientific concepts, personal stories, and multimedia elements. Covering topics ranging from physics and biology to everyday phenomena, the show translates scientific knowledge into engaging and thought-provoking experiences for broad public audiences.

Innovation factor: The project innovatively merges science communication with professional stand-up comedy, using humour to challenge misconceptions and make complex ideas more approachable. Rather than simplifying science into facts alone, it invites audiences to question assumptions, embrace uncertainty, and engage with scientific thinking through laughter and storytelling.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain exposure to scientific concepts in a memorable and accessible format, increasing their confidence and interest in science. The show promotes positive attitudes toward scientific inquiry while encouraging audiences to think more critically about the world around them, question common beliefs, and remain open to evidence-based perspectives.

GEDI considerations: Stand-Up Science is designed to reach diverse audiences beyond traditional science engagement settings.

Limitations found: N/A

3.7 #StandUpScience

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Title: #StandUpScience

Contributor: IDIBELL

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2019

Website: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLoTRYZtZYhLM3YLEHrG78mLznw_zQePzO

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Parks and gardens

Main objective: The main objective of #StandUpScience is to empower young researchers to communicate their work beyond academic settings, using humour, storytelling, and creativity to make science more accessible. It seeks to strengthen the connection between research and society while encouraging audiences to engage critically with scientific questions and their impact on everyday life.

Summary of initiative: #StandUpScience is a science communication initiative in which early-career researchers create and perform short stand-up-style talks and videos based on their own research. Through training in communication and performance techniques, researchers translate complex topics into engaging narratives that invite the public to explore science from a more personal and relatable perspective.

Innovation factor: The project places young researchers—not professional communicators—at the centre of public engagement. By combining scientific expertise with performance, digital media, and humour, it humanises researchers and challenges stereotypes about who scientists are.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a better understanding of current research and the people behind it. Seeing young scientists communicate directly about their work helps demystify science, increases trust in research, and makes scientific careers appear more accessible. The format encourages curiosity, critical thinking, and a greater willingness to engage with scientific evidence and societal challenges.

GEDI considerations: By showcasing a diverse group of early-career researchers and their personal journeys, the project helps challenge stereotypes related to science, age, gender, and professional identity. The informal and accessible format lowers barriers to engagement, allowing audiences from different backgrounds to connect with science through authentic voices and experiences. The visibility of young researchers also provides relatable role models for students and groups traditionally underrepresented in STEM.

Limitations found: N/A

3.8 Transmedia_Lab Mandarinina

Title: Transmedia_Lab Mandarinina

Contributor: La Mandarinina de Newton

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2019

Website: <https://open.spotify.com/show/39RsQoa80sJf1w4s0Xms3j>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Health and wellbeing and science and humanistic culture

Venues: It can be done indoors and outdoors, but you need recording equipment

Main objective: The main objective of this podcast series is to foster open, participatory dialogue between experts and the public on a wide range of scientific, artistic, and humanistic topics. By incorporating live audiences and interactive questioning, the project aims to make knowledge exchange more accessible, reflective, and socially relevant for adult audiences.

Summary of initiative: This is a live-recorded podcast series designed for adult audiences, where each episode explores interdisciplinary themes spanning science, research, current affairs, arts, and humanities. Episodes are recorded in front of a public audience, and at the end of each session, attendees are invited to ask questions and engage directly with the speakers, turning the podcast into a hybrid format between public talk and broadcast media.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining podcasting with live public engagement, transforming a traditionally passive medium into an interactive event. The integration of diverse disciplinary perspectives alongside real-time audience participation encourages open-ended dialogue, embraces complexity, and creates space for uncertainty, debate, and multiple viewpoints.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain accessible insights into complex and interdisciplinary topics while being actively involved in shaping the conversation. The live Q&A format promotes critical thinking, deeper engagement with content, and a more reflective attitude towards science, culture, and society. It also strengthens the perception of knowledge as something dynamic, shared, and open to questioning.

GEDI considerations: The project supports inclusion by opening expert discussions to public participation in an accessible and informal setting. The diversity of topics helps engage audiences with different interests and backgrounds.

Limitations found: N/A

3.9 Desafíos del Océano: científicas al Mando

Title: Desafíos del Océano: científicas al Mando

Contributor: Universidad de Vigo

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: <https://www.divulgateca.es/Proyecto-destacado.aspx?Id=1431>

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Oceans

Venues: The initiative combined online audiovisual dissemination with activities in research centres, marine laboratories, schools, and public communication channels.

Main objective: The main objective of the project is to bring marine science closer to society through the work and perspectives of women researchers working on major ocean challenges such as marine plastics, coastal erosion, ocean acidification, invasive species, extreme events, and sustainable fisheries. The initiative also aims to reduce gender stereotypes in marine science and inspire future scientific vocations among young people.

Summary of initiative: Desafíos del Océano: Científicas al Mando is a six-episode documentary miniseries in which leading women marine scientists present their research on urgent ocean and climate-related challenges. Each 15-minute episode explores a key topic in marine science through accessible storytelling and personal narratives. The project also included a national competition for science-track high school students, offering selected participants the opportunity to spend time in research laboratories with the featured scientists.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining short-form documentary storytelling, science communication, and gender representation in a highly accessible audiovisual format adapted to contemporary digital consumption habits.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Audiences gain greater understanding of current marine and environmental challenges while developing closer emotional connections to scientific research and the people behind it. The initiative increases ocean literacy, raises awareness about sustainability and climate issues, and helps challenge stereotypes about women in STEM careers. For participating students, the laboratory immersion experience can strengthen scientific vocations and improve perceptions of research careers as accessible and socially meaningful.

GEDI considerations: Gender equality is central to the project, as it explicitly foregrounds women scientists in fields where gender gaps have historically existed. By showcasing diverse female role models in marine research, the initiative contributes to breaking stereotypes and encouraging young women to pursue scientific careers.

Limitations found: N/A

3.10 MurCIENCIA

Title: MurCIENCIA

Contributor: Universidad de Murcia

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2000

Website: https://www.um.es/web/murciencia/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: The initiative takes place in public urban spaces, historical city centres, cultural heritage sites, and through digital platforms and mobile applications.

Main objective: The main objective of MurCIENCIA is to bring science closer to society by revealing the scientific dimensions hidden within everyday urban spaces, local history, and cultural heritage. The project seeks to increase public interest in science, stimulate citizen participation, and position scientific knowledge as part of the cultural and touristic identity of the region.

Summary of initiative: MurCIENCIA is a scientific tourism and urban science communication project that offers interactive city routes connecting emblematic locations with scientific stories, discoveries, and historical figures. Through marked itineraries, mobile technologies, QR codes, and gamified content, participants explore the relationship between science, history, architecture, language, climate, and local culture in accessible and engaging ways.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by transforming the city itself into an open-air science museum where scientific knowledge emerges through urban exploration and cultural tourism. By combining physical routes, digital interaction, storytelling, and gamification, MurCIENCIA creates a hybrid model between tourism, citizen engagement, and science communication that embeds science into everyday public space and collective memory.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop greater awareness of the scientific dimensions of their urban environment and local heritage, while strengthening curiosity and engagement with science in informal contexts. The project encourages citizens and visitors to see science as part of daily life rather than something confined to laboratories or academic institutions.

GEDI considerations: MurCIENCIA promotes inclusive access to science through free and publicly accessible routes designed for diverse audiences regardless of age, educational background, or prior scientific knowledge.

Limitations found: N/A

3.11 Disseminating Science through Theatre

Title: Disseminating Science through Theatre

Contributor: CRAG

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: https://www.cragenomica.es/outreach/disseminating-science-through-theatre?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities, soil and agrogenomics.

Venues: Activities take place in theatres, civic centres, schools, universities, cultural institutions, festivals, and research centres

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Main objective: The main objective of the initiative is to engage audiences with scientific knowledge and the human stories behind research through theatrical performance. By dramatizing scientific discoveries, ethical tensions, and the lives of researchers, the project seeks to make science emotionally accessible, socially relevant, and open to public reflection and dialogue.

Summary of initiative: The project develops theatrical productions inspired by scientific events, discoveries, or researchers' lives, combining scientific accuracy with artistic interpretation. Through scripts, performances, staged readings, and participatory discussions, audiences are invited to explore scientific concepts not only intellectually but also emotionally and socially. In the CRAG project, for example, the life and discoveries of geneticist Barbara McClintock were transformed into a collaborative theatre production involving scientists, drama students, and educators.

Innovation factor: The initiative innovates by using theatre as a space where science becomes embodied, emotional, and ethically complex rather than purely informational. Instead of presenting science as neutral or distant, dramatization exposes uncertainty, conflict, creativity, and the personal dimensions of scientific work.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Audiences gain greater understanding of scientific concepts and research processes while also developing empathy toward the people behind scientific discoveries. The performative and emotional nature of theatre encourages critical thinking, curiosity, and deeper reflection on the societal and ethical implications of science. These experiences can help transform perceptions of science from something abstract and inaccessible into something human, cultural, and participatory.

GEDI considerations: Science theatre initiatives can promote inclusion by presenting diverse scientific role models and making scientific topics accessible through storytelling, emotion, and collective experience rather than technical language alone. Projects such as the dramatization of Barbara McClintock's life also contribute to increasing the visibility of women scientists and challenging historical gender biases in science representation.

Limitations found: N/A

3.12 EcoScienceCircus

Title: EcoScienceCircus

Contributor: INOVA+

Country of implementation: Portugal

Start date of initiative: 2010

Website: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265651?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Activities were delivered in high-visibility public spaces such as urban seafronts, science festivals, open-air events, and cultural gatherings. A flagship event was organised in Matosinhos (Portugal), attracting thousands of participants and wide public visibility.

Main objective: The main objective was to bring science closer to society by breaking stereotypes about researchers and making scientific work more visible, engaging, and emotionally accessible through contemporary circus performance. The project particularly emphasised ecology and sustainability as urgent societal challenges.

Summary of initiative: EcoScienceCircus used contemporary circus arts—such as acrobatics, movement, and performance storytelling—to communicate scientific themes related to ecology and sustainable development. Researchers and performers co-created public shows where scientific ideas were embedded in artistic acts, transforming complex environmental issues into engaging, visual, and emotional experiences for broad audiences.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in using contemporary circus as a narrative and communication tool for science, replacing traditional lecture-based outreach with embodied, spectacular, and emotionally engaging performance.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Audiences develop greater awareness of sustainability and environmental science while also shifting perceptions of researchers, seeing them as creative and approachable.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

GEDI considerations: The project promotes inclusion by using non-verbal, performative, and visual communication formats that are accessible across different ages, education levels, and cultural backgrounds.

Limitations found: N/A.

4. Dialogue and engagement

4.1 Smog tasting

Title: Smog tasting

Contributor: The Centre for Genomic Gastronomy

Country of implementation: London, Los Angeles, Atlanta, Beijing, Mumbai

Start date of initiative: 2017

Website: <https://genomicgastronomy.com/work/2017-2/smog-tasting-take-out/>

Target group: EDU, CIV and UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer

Venues: include both traditional and non-formal community spaces - such as botanic gardens, parks, libraries, marketplaces and board game cafés - to broaden access to science and stimulate engagement in everyday environments.

Main objective: Smog tasting shifts the invisible, unconscious act of breathing into the highly visceral act of eating. It confronts people with their local ecological footprint, highlighting that we are already ingesting this pollution daily.

Summary of initiative: Smog Tasting uses egg foams to harvest air pollution from around the world. Participants are sent a Smog Tasting Kit and are asked to capture their city's smog in the batter of meringue cookies. Participants then ship a batch of smog meringues to a central location where the Smog Tasting: Take Out event can taste and compare a range of international smog meringues. Smog Tasting is an award-winning conceptual art project that turns air pollution into desserts.

Innovation factor: Smog Tasting street cart makes urban air quality tangible by harvesting air from highly polluted areas and serving it in meringue form. Egg foams are up to 90 percent air, and whipping the eggs causes particulate matter to be trapped in the batter. The batter can be tested for heavy metals and VOCs, compared in a microscope or baked and served as "Trojan horse" sweets. The custom Smog Tasting cart will feature a portable smog chamber and will serve up free, edible smog meringues from different cities and eras, as well as printed materials, including field guides to smog harvesting and suggested food pairings. The cart, decorated with supergraphics displaying air-quality data, also serves as a base for smog harvesting workshops.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: As one of the main ingredients is the air that we breathe everyday, the served treats are not hazardous. Instead they act as a reminder of the importance of air quality and offer a way of understanding what smog is. The effects of smog can be deadly, but because of its invisibility and the long time it takes for the health backlash to manifest, it's hard to alert people to its threats.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

4.2 Pint of Science

Title: Pint of science

Contributor: N/A

Country of implementation: International

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: <https://pintofscience.es/>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, and Science in Summer

Venues: Include non-formal community spaces - such cafés and bars - to broaden access to science and stimulate engagement in everyday environments.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Main objective: Pint of science makes cutting-edge scientific knowledge accessible and engaging, raises awareness of current research and innovation, fosters connections between researchers and society, and inspires curiosity and lifelong learning.

Summary of initiative: Pint of Science is an international science communication festival that takes science out of traditional academic spaces and into bars, cafés, and other everyday venues. Over several days, researchers share their work through short, engaging talks and discussions, allowing audiences to interact directly with scientists and explore a wide range of topics, from health and climate change to technology, astronomy, and society.

Innovation factor: Pint of Science lies has the ability to transform informal social spaces into venues for science engagement. By bringing researchers into environments where people naturally gather, the initiative removes barriers between science and society, fostering open conversations and making scientific knowledge more approachable and enjoyable.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The initiative increases public awareness and understanding of current scientific research while encouraging curiosity and critical thinking. Direct interactions with researchers help demystify science, build trust in scientific expertise, and foster more positive attitudes towards research and innovation. The informal format also encourages audiences to engage actively in scientific discussions and to view science as a relevant part of everyday life.

GEDI considerations: Pint of Science promotes inclusiveness by bringing science into accessible community spaces and presenting topics in language that does not require prior scientific knowledge. Its broad thematic coverage and diverse range of speakers help engage audiences with different interests, backgrounds, and levels of education. By lowering participation barriers and encouraging dialogue, the initiative supports wider and more equitable access to science communication.

Limitations found: N/A

4.3 Science pairing

Title: Science pairing

Contributor: La Mandarina de Newton

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2013

Website: N/A

Target group: ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cities, Science in summer, Health and wellbeing

Venues: include non-formal community spaces - such parks, marketplaces, shops, cafés and bars - to broaden access to science and stimulate engagement in everyday environments.

Main objective: Science pairing makes cutting-edge scientific knowledge accessible and engaging, raises awareness of current research and innovation, fosters connections between researchers and society, and inspires curiosity and lifelong learning.

Summary of initiative: Series of conferences dedicated to exploring frontier scientific research, accompanied by local wines and thematic food and beverage pairings, fostering an engaging and informal environment for discussion and learning.

Innovation factor: Science Pairing introduces an innovative science engagement model that brings frontier scientific research into everyday community spaces where people naturally gather. By integrating science communication, local gastronomy, and informal dialogue, it creates a multisensory and participatory experience that makes science more accessible, memorable, and engaging. The initiative strengthens connections between researchers and society and it fosters partnerships between the scientific community, local businesses, and cultural heritage sectors.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Science Pairing is expected to enhance participants' understanding of frontier scientific research and its societal relevance, foster positive attitudes toward science and local heritage, encourage lifelong learning and engagement in science-related activities, and promote dialogue, critical thinking, and evidence-based decision-making.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

4.4 Science reading club

Title: Science reading clubs

Contributor: Biblioteca Sagrada Família, Barcelona

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, and Science In Summer.

Venues: Collaborate with libraries to integrate science topics into readers' everyday reading habits.

Main objective: Science reading clubs promote lifelong learning through science-related literature.

Summary of initiative: Science reading clubs bring together community members to discuss science-related books and articles. It provides an informal setting for learning, discussion, and critical thinking about scientific topics and their relevance to society.

Innovation factor: Science reading clubs offer an innovative approach to public engagement by integrating scientific topics into everyday reading and cultural practices. By combining science with literature and the humanities, they create spaces for dialogue and reflection on both the scientific and societal dimensions of contemporary challenges.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Science reading clubs are expected to increase participants' knowledge of scientific topics and their social, ethical, and cultural dimensions. By combining science with literature and the humanities, they foster positive attitudes toward science, critical reflection, and openness to diverse perspectives. They encourage lifelong reading and learning habits and stimulate informed discussion of science-related issues.

GEDI considerations: By exploring science and history through diverse voices and perspectives, and fostering guided discussion, the activity enhances understanding of gender and diversity issues while promoting inclusion and critical thinking.

Limitations found: N/A

4.5 Living Libraries

Title: Living Libraries

Contributor: Comune di Genova

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: https://www.visitgenoa.it/it/la-biblioteca-vivente?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer

Venues: Public libraries, but potentially other public spaces (parks, schools, squares, markets...)

Main objective: Raising awareness on cancer with a focus on prevention, treatment, real-life experiences.

Summary of initiative: In a living library, people become living books sharing their personal experiences on cancer. This format creates a space where patients, caregivers and patient's family members, doctors, survivors can share their personal stories.

Innovation factor: In a living library topics related to cancer are dealt with in an interactive and human-centered experience, capable of raising awareness and emotional connection. The format is flexible as it can be held in several places (libraries, schools, public spaces...).

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: A living library on cancer can contribute to raise awareness and knowledge, to reduce fear and normalize an open conversation on cancer and to reduce stereotypes. This activity can develop empathy and contribute to fight isolation.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: There could be some reluctance from the audience due to emotional burden.

4.6 Science BiblioBus

Title: Science Bibliobus (original title: Biblioguagua)

Contributor: Tenerife City Council

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 1977

Website: https://www.bibliotecaspublicas.es/santacruztenerife/Descripcion_Centros/biblioguagua-biblioexpres/Conoce_mas.html

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer.

Venues: Make science more accessible to small rural communities

Main objective: Science Bibliobus enhances access to science and encourages lifelong learning across diverse communities.

Summary of initiative: A mobile science outreach activity that brings books, experiments, and interactive learning experiences to different communities through a traveling science bibliobus. Designed for all ages, it promotes curiosity, scientific culture, and public engagement with science in an accessible and informal environment.

Innovation factor: Science Bibliobus brings science directly to communities and can be tailored to special occasions, including local festivals and summer holiday activities.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: By bringing science directly to communities, Science Bibliobus is expected to increase participants' knowledge of scientific topics and their relevance to everyday life, foster positive attitudes toward science by making it more accessible and familiar, and encourage behaviours such as reading science-related materials, engaging in lifelong learning, and participating in community science activities.

GEDI considerations: This initiative is aimed at rural areas that have historically been underserved in science communication and public engagement activities, helping to reduce geographic disparities in access to science knowledge.

Limitations found: N/A

4.7 Augmented City: City, culture and science

Title: Ciutat augmentada: Ciutat, cultura i ciència

Contributor: La Mandarina de Newton

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2020

Website: <http://www.ciutatculturaiciencia.barcelona/>

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities

Venues: Augmented City is a set of science-focused urban itineraries situated within the city, from which audiences can choose according to their interests.

Main objective: To reinterpret the city as an open-air museum where citizens can explore science, culture, and history through self-guided thematic routes. The initiative aims to encourage citizens to discover and connect with their urban environment by linking real places with curated narratives and audiovisual content accessible through a digital platform.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Summary of initiative: The project offers a set of curated, self-guided urban routes that transform Barcelona into an augmented cultural and scientific landscape. Users can choose different itineraries that guide them through specific themes, connecting physical locations in the city with videos, stories, and contextual information. Although experts may be featured in audiovisual materials, the experience itself is designed as an independent exploration journey, allowing users to engage with the city at their own pace.

Innovation factor: The initiative innovatively combines digital storytelling, augmented cultural heritage, and place-based learning by turning the city into an interactive museum. Instead of relying on guided tours or live mediation, it empowers users to actively construct their own experience by selecting routes and connecting digital narratives with real urban spaces, blending physical exploration with multimedia content.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The experience enhances participants' understanding of the city's scientific, cultural, and historical dimensions by linking abstract narratives to real locations. It encourages curiosity, observation, and active exploration of the urban environment, fostering a more engaged and reflective relationship with the city and its hidden layers of knowledge.

GEDI considerations: The digital and self-guided nature of the initiative promotes accessibility by allowing users to engage with the content at their own pace, according to their interests and needs. The diversity of routes and themes supports multiple entry points for different audiences, helping to include people with varied backgrounds, levels of knowledge, and cultural perspectives, while reducing barriers linked to formal guided experiences.

Limitations found: N/A

4.8 Urban itinerary

Title: Urban itinerary

Contributor: EJP Paleontology Conference in Lisbon

Country of implementation: Portugal

Start date of initiative: 2009

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities, Soil, Science In Summer, and Careers in R&I

Venues: The city

Main objective: The main objective of the Urban Itinerary project is to enhance public understanding of the relationship between science, architecture, and the urban environment. Through guided exploration of the city, participants learn about the geological origins, properties, and uses of building materials, fostering greater awareness of how scientific knowledge shapes the spaces we live in.

Summary of initiative: The Urban Itinerary is a participatory educational activity that takes participants on a guided tour through the city to discover the scientific stories behind its buildings and infrastructure. By examining architectural elements and construction materials, participants explore topics such as geology, material science, urban development, and sustainability, connecting scientific concepts to everyday urban landscapes.

Innovation factor: The project transforms the city itself into an open-air learning environment, making science accessible through direct observation and real-world examples. By linking architecture, geology, and environmental science in an interactive format, the initiative offers an engaging and interdisciplinary approach to science communication that encourages participants to view familiar urban spaces through a scientific lens.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop a deeper understanding of the scientific principles behind building materials, urban design, and resource use. The activity encourages curiosity about the built environment and promotes appreciation for the role of science in shaping sustainable and resilient cities. As a result, participants may become more informed and engaged citizens, with greater awareness of environmental and urban sustainability issues.

GEDI considerations: The Urban Itinerary is designed to be accessible and inclusive, welcoming participants from diverse backgrounds, ages, and levels of scientific knowledge. The use of public urban spaces as learning environments helps reduce barriers to participation, while the interdisciplinary nature of the activity allows for multiple perspectives and forms of engagement. Efforts can be made to ensure physical accessibility, inclusive communication, and representation of diverse contributions to science, architecture, and urban development.

Limitations found: N/A

4.9 Student-led Multi-platform Bioscience Communication Initiative

Title: Student-led Multi-platform Bioscience Communication Initiative

Contributor: DNA Voyagers (Student Science Group in Biology & Biotechnology)

Country of implementation: Greece

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: <https://dnavoyagers.weebly.com/>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Careers in R&I - with events that promote research and innovation career paths

Venues: Schools, universities, science festivals, conferences, public engagement events, and online platforms.

Main objective: To communicate biology and biotechnology in an accessible and engaging way through student-led science communication activities.

Summary of initiative: DNA Voyagers is a student-led initiative that promotes biology and biotechnology through an open-access student journal, social media communication, and participation in outreach events, science festivals, and school activities. The initiative focuses on peer-to-peer communication, helping students and non-specialist audiences engage with scientific topics in a relatable and understandable way.

Innovation factor: The initiative combines digital publishing, social media outreach, and in-person engagement into a student-driven, multi-platform communication model. Its peer-to-peer approach makes science more relatable and accessible while strengthening the connection between academic research and society.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: DNA Voyagers increases interest and understanding of biosciences by presenting scientific concepts in accessible formats. The initiative encourages curiosity, supports science literacy, and promotes positive attitudes toward careers in research and innovation.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promotes accessibility and inclusion by using clear, understandable language and peer-based communication formats that reduce barriers between scientific communities and the public.

Limitations found: As a volunteer-based student initiative, DNA Voyagers faces limitations related to funding, institutional support, long-term sustainability, and the measurement of long-term audience impact across multiple communication channels.

4.10 Behind the Curtain of Science

Title: Behind the Curtain of Science

Contributor: Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences

Country of implementation: Czechia

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://www.fzu.cz/en/for-the-public/outreach-events/theater-days-fzu>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, and Cities and Soil.

Venues: What normally functions as a lecture hall has been transformed into an informal theatre for the duration of the event. Any theatre or community center would be good for running a related event.

Main objective: Behind the Curtain of Science aims to engage people with science through dramatic storytelling and subsequent active participation in discussions with artists and scientists.

Summary of initiative: Behind the Curtain of Science is a scicomm festival that presents scientific topics through the performing arts. The first instance (in November 2025) combined drama, modern dance and stand-up to explore scientific ideas, science history narratives and ethical dilemmas in science. It included original plays, a dance performance inspired by particle physics and cosmology, science stand-up from FameLab CZ finalists and the staging of established science-theatre works such as Michael Frayn's Copenhagen. The initiative is part of the Institute of Physics's outreach and science art activities and aims to engage broad audiences, from school students to the general public, by offering free performances and discussions with scientists and artists. It also serves as a platform for original science-theatre productions and encourages their reuse and adaptation through open licensing (the first play written specifically for the festival, The Martians, has been released under the Creative Commons license). The second instance of the festival will be held in Nov. 2026, and they are looking to expand it to international guest performers and audiences in 2027.

Innovation factor: Science theater events are still a rare form of scicomm and engagement, and even more so in the Czech context where we held the event. It's innovative in its integration of scientific content with multiple performing-arts formats (theatre, dance, stand-up) into a single, cohesive festival. A key element is the commissioning and open sharing of original science theatre works, which can be adapted for educational and outreach purposes beyond the event itself. In the Czech context, the festival represents a novel format: a dedicated science theatre event bringing together artists and scientists in a structured programme. By positioning performing arts not just as a tool but as a partner in scicomm, the local methodological repertoire of public engagement with science is widened.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Science theater events are still a rare form of scicomm and engagement, and even more so in the Czech context. Its integration of scientific content with multiple performing-arts formats, uses narrative, emotion and artistic expression to communicate science, deepen interest in it and directly engage audiences. Original theatre productions, stand-up science performances, dance interpretations of physical phenomena are followed by subsequent discussions with experts, demonstrating a multidisciplinary approach to science communication. This diversity enables the exploration of scientific topics from various perspectives.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: Not all performances included a direct engagement component; however, most did include a discussion with active audience participation, and this year they are aiming to include workshops. Funding can also be limited, bringing additional struggle.

4.11 Game Cafés

Title: Game Cafés

Contributor: Science Melting Pot

Country of implementation: Italy, Belgium, Denmark

Start date of initiative: 2019

Website: <https://www.sciencemeltingpot.com/portfolio/quantum-game-cafe>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Quantum Technology

Venues: Science Festival, Cafés, Pubs

Main objective: Build curiosity and make quantum physics less intimidating, especially to those who have never heard about the topic or just starting out.

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Summary of initiative: It was an event in 2019 to popularize quantum physics through games, both analogue and digital games. The event took place at a local café where anyone could come by to play games and learn about the interesting concepts of quantum physics.

Innovation factor: Games as the learning tool.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The format was impactful in changing the attitude and behaviour of the target audience. Participants went back home wanting to know more about quantum physics and technology. Also, they were less intimidated by the topic. Typically, we see that people don't engage with quantum technology topics because they think they have to be smart or intelligent to understand it. This format with games removes that barrier, as games are in the centre and the curiosity around quantum physics is what is built as a consequence.

GEDI considerations: We wanted to ensure in creating an environment where the topic is accessible to all, and where people feel valued, respected and heard.

Limitations found: It becomes limited to curiosity building and may not translate to learning the scientific concept in depth.

4.12 Kaleidoscope Dialogues: Science, Society, and Conversation

Title: Kaleidoscope Dialogues: Science, Society, and Conversation

Contributor: Kaleidoscope Dialogues

Country of implementation: Germany

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: <https://www.kaleidoscopediologues.com/>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Natural and social sciences.

Venues: Bars, cultural centres, restaurants, and other informal community spaces.

Main objective: To encourage open and accessible conversations on scientific topics through interactive and informal public events.

Summary of initiative: Kaleidoscope Dialogues is a non-profit, volunteer-based science communication initiative that connects researchers and the public through interactive talks, panel discussions, exhibitions, and games in relaxed social environments. The project promotes dialogue around STEM, social sciences, and humanities topics while making science more approachable, understandable, and connected to everyday life.

Innovation factor: The initiative innovates science communication by combining interdisciplinary scientific discussions with informal social settings that encourage participation, dialogue, and interaction rather than one-way dissemination. Its use of diverse formats and community-based venues helps reduce barriers between academia and society.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Kaleidoscope Dialogues increases public interest in science by exposing audiences to accessible research topics and encouraging active participation. The initiative promotes curiosity, improves perceptions of researchers and science, and fosters ongoing engagement through repeat attendance and community collaborations.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promotes diversity and inclusion through an international and interdisciplinary organizing team and by prioritizing diverse speakers and topics related to gender, culture, language, and social inclusion in science and society.

Limitations found: As a volunteer-based initiative, Kaleidoscope Dialogues faces challenges related to funding, event logistics, venue availability, and coordination across geographically dispersed team members, which may affect long-term sustainability and expansion.

4.13 Exploring the Microcosm: Foldscope Science Across India

Title: Exploring the Microcosm: Foldscope Science Across India

D1.1 – 'Science4Everyone' Inspirational Formats

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Contributor: Stanford University

Country of implementation: India and USA

Start date of initiative: 2020

Website: <https://www.sciencemeltingpot.com/portfolio/quantum-game-cafe>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities, Soil; Science in Summer, biodiversity, ecology, and the microscopic world.

Venues: Rural schools, tribal communities, mountain villages, urban slums, and other non-formal community spaces across India.

Main objective: To provide children in remote and underserved communities with hands-on access to science and ecological learning using the Foldscope, an ultra-low-cost paper microscope.

Summary of initiative: The initiative uses Foldscope microscopes to introduce children to microorganisms found in their local environments, including soil fungi, algae, bacteria, and plant cells. Through direct observation of samples collected from nearby ecosystems, participants explore scientific concepts linked to biodiversity, environmental health, and climate resilience in an accessible and place-based way, without requiring laboratories or expensive infrastructure.

Innovation factor: The project combines low-cost scientific tools, community participation, and Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) to create a citizen-science model rooted in local environmental realities. By encouraging communities to document and study their own ecosystems, the initiative transforms science learning into a participatory and culturally relevant experience with future potential for digital biodiversity archiving.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The workshops improve scientific literacy and environmental awareness by making invisible microbial life visible and understandable. Participants develop curiosity about hygiene, biodiversity, and ecosystem health, often continuing observations and environmental discussions within their families and communities after the workshops.

GEDI considerations: The initiative prioritizes communities with limited access to science education, including girls, tribal populations, Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe communities, and students in remote areas. Activities are adapted to local languages and cultural contexts to support inclusive participation.

Limitations found: The initiative currently depends on limited personnel and funding, restricting its geographic scale and long-term continuity. Additional challenges include maintaining community engagement, training local facilitators, and overcoming limited internet connectivity for digital documentation in remote regions.

4.14 Mind the Lab

Title: Mind the Lab

Contributor: SciCo - Science Communication

Country of implementation: Greece, UK, Ireland, Germany, Spain and others

Start date of initiative: 2016

Website: <https://scico.gr/en/activities/mindthelab/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): A wide range of topics has been showcased.

Venues: It takes place a) at the Metro, a venue where several thousands of people pass by everyday b) at Science Festivals (MEDNIGHT, Athens Science Festival etc)

Main objective: Mind the Lab was founded to engage the general public in a dynamic science communication experience, acting as a teaser to spark interest and direct people toward further scientific activities. By promoting scientific and technological literacy to a wider audience, the project aims to provide citizens with the tools necessary to participate thoughtfully and confidently in an

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

increasingly technological world. Furthermore, the initiative seeks to foster innovation by connecting researchers and scientists directly with the public, ultimately creating new opportunities for prosperous collaborations and impactful networking.

Summary of initiative: Mind the Lab, inspired by the well-known “mind the gap” notice in metro stations, is a breakthrough science communication approach that aims to bring science to the general public. The idea behind this project is to bring science closer to people, by organizing outreach events, in places, where thousands of people, who don't necessarily have a pre-existing interest in science, pass by: The Metro. Impressive scientific experiments, innovative technological applications, interactive games, and artistic events demonstrated by enthusiastic scientists, make up the activities in each station. In that way, people of all ages, interests, and levels of scientific literacy, have the opportunity to become engaged with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), helping stimulate a curiosity they may not have even realised they had.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in the fact that, instead of expecting people to encounter science in traditional settings such as science festivals, institutes or universities, this approach targets audiences who would not normally seek out science-related activities. Rather than “asking” people to come to science, science is brought directly to them through short, engaging activities in everyday public spaces such as metro stations. The “wow factor” is essential. Interactive exhibits, activities designed for mixed audiences, and short, easy-to-repeat scientific experiments or impressive exhibits, help capture the attention of passers-by and spark curiosity in unexpected moments.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Mind the Lab activities aim to increase curiosity and challenge the idea that science is only for experts by connecting science to everyday life. Participants gain basic understanding of the concepts behind the experiments, while engaging with professionals from diverse scientific fields and learning about emerging technologies and current research. It changes attitudes mainly by reshaping how people perceive science and their relationship with it. Mind the Lab moves people from passive observers to active participants, even in small ways: like stopping, exploring, asking and following up on science after the experience.

GEDI considerations: Mind the Lab is designed as a free, open-access public science engagement activity that ensures inclusion of all citizens, regardless of gender, age, educational background or social status. Activities take place in public spaces, allowing equal access for people who would not typically engage with science in formal settings. It is implemented in accessible public environments and uses visual, hands-on and interactive formats.

Limitations found: The environments are often crowded and noisy and the engagement with the public is usually brief as people hurry to their destinations. Additionally, executing these initiatives requires formal agreements with the urban railway company or local public space authorities.

4.15 Science in the Kitchen

Title: Science in the kitchen

Contributor: Associazione Festival della Scienza

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2004

Website: <https://festival2025.festivalscienza.it/programma-2025/scienza-in-cucina-20>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Science festivals, markets, historical places, etc

Main objective: Let people understand that science is everywhere, also in us and in what we eat (all chemicals).

Summary of initiative: Science in the kitchen includes workshops on food in general or on a specific one, conferences between a scientist and a chef, special events, show cooking, market tour with a scientist, show cooking in order to let people understand that science is really everywhere and that all we eat is chemistry; or conferences on how to prevent diseases connected with food.

Innovation factor: It's a neverending subject since you can approach in different ways, and innovation in kitchen is always in motion and emotion: microwaves ovens, induction air frying are all innovation in food; hundreds of new receipts to make new dishes with new ingredients even from algae, insects or from different continents; new discoveries about perception of tastes, new discoveries about diseases and they relationship with food are always good news to disseminates.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: People are always interested in what they eat and it's easier to disseminate new contents, ideas, and to surprise them with information about the food they usually eat without reflecting on it.

GEDI considerations: Food is an inclusive subject that can bring people together, but it's also a diverse subject: vegan, vegetarian, allergies.

Limitations found: While highly effective in generating curiosity and engagement, the format may have limited capacity to support deeper understanding of complex scientific concepts beyond introductory exploration.

4.16 Shake up your curiosity at Science Cocktails

Title: Shake up your curiosity at Science Cocktails

Contributor: Exploratorium

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://www.exploratorium.edu/press-office/press-releases/shake-your-curiosity-science-cocktails-0>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Science Museum

Main objective: To engage adult audiences with science through an enjoyable and accessible experience that connects scientific concepts to the familiar world of food, beverages, and everyday phenomena.

Summary of initiative: Science of Cocktails is an annual, interactive after-party where science meets mixology. At Science of Cocktails, guests will uncover the phenomena behind their favorite drinks while enjoying a vibrant, science of color-themed celebration. Attendees are encouraged to dress in striking monochromatic outfits to fully immerse themselves in the evening's theme. It includes an open bar, creative food and beverages, hands-on science, and dynamic entertainment, all in support of the museum's many community and public programs which inspire learners of all ages.

Innovation factor: The initiative combines science communication with cocktail culture, creating an unconventional environment for learning. By integrating scientific demonstrations, experiments, and interactions with experts into a social event, it attracts audiences who may not typically participate in science-related activities.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The initiative increases awareness of the scientific principles underlying everyday experiences, making science more approachable and engaging. It fosters positive attitudes towards science and encourages participants to explore scientific topics with greater curiosity and confidence

GEDI considerations: Ensure creating an environment where the topic is accessible to all, and where people feel valued, respected and heard.

Limitations found: By using a social and informal format, the initiative lowers barriers to participation and reaches audiences beyond traditional science-engaged communities. The combination of science, culture, and everyday experiences broadens the appeal of scientific topics and supports a more inclusive approach to public engagement.

4.17 Science ice cream van

Title: Science ice cream van

Contributor: Ciência Viva and Centro Ciência Viva do Algarve

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Country of implementation: Portugal

Start date of initiative: 2025 (within the Ciência Viva no Verão programme, active nationally since 1996)

Website: https://www.cienciaviva.pt/verao/2025/?acao=showactivities&id_activity=8736

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Public spaces including parks, beaches, promenades, science festivals, and urban outdoor areas. The 2025 edition took place in Faro between Jardim Manuel Bivar and Cais da Porta Nova.

Main objective: To make science accessible, engaging, and enjoyable through short interactive activities that connect everyday experiences with scientific concepts in informal public settings.

Summary of initiative: The Science Ice Cream Van is a mobile science communication activity developed as part of the Ciência Viva no Verão programme. Inspired by the format of an ice cream cart, participants can choose different “science ice creams,” each representing a short hands-on scientific activity, experiment, or demonstration. Moving through public outdoor spaces, the initiative creates playful opportunities for children, families, and passers-by to engage with scientific topics ranging from the ocean and biodiversity to astronomy and environmental science.

Innovation factor: The initiative transforms a familiar and playful urban object—the ice cream van—into a mobile science engagement space that brings science directly into everyday public environments. By combining mobility, sensory experiences, and short interactive activities, it creates an accessible and highly engaging science communication format outside traditional educational institutions.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The activity promotes curiosity and positive attitudes toward science by presenting scientific concepts through informal, hands-on participation. Its approachable format encourages audiences of different ages and backgrounds to interact with science in a relaxed and memorable way, helping reduce barriers to scientific engagement.

GEDI considerations: The initiative supports inclusive participation by taking science directly into accessible public spaces and using simple, interactive formats suitable for diverse audiences, including children, families, tourists, and people with different levels of scientific literacy. The activity is also identified as accessible within the Ciência Viva programme.

Limitations found: Due to its short and highly informal format, the initiative mainly supports introductory engagement and curiosity-building rather than in-depth scientific learning or long-term participant follow-up.

4.18 Supermarket Sweep: The CoDiet Escape Room

Title: Supermarket Sweep: The CoDiet Escape Room

Contributor: Imperial College London

Country of implementation: United Kingdom

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://www.codiet.eu/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, diet, health, and personalised nutrition.

Venues: Science museums, universities, festivals, classrooms, and public market spaces.

Main objective: To engage diverse audiences with research on diet, health, artificial intelligence, and personalised nutrition through an accessible and interactive escape room experience.

Summary of initiative: Supermarket Sweep: The CoDiet Escape Room is a portable pop-up activity that places participants inside a fictional “Supermarket of the Future.” Working in teams, players solve puzzles, collect groceries, and complete challenges linked to personalised nutrition, AI, and non-communicable diseases before time runs out. Developed as part of the CoDiet project, the activity transforms complex interdisciplinary research into a playful and relatable public engagement experience.

Innovation factor: The initiative uses an immersive escape room format to communicate interdisciplinary scientific research through storytelling, teamwork, and problem-solving. By situating scientific concepts in the familiar setting of a supermarket and using a modular pop-up design, the project creates accessible science engagement opportunities in both formal and informal public spaces.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The activity increases awareness of personalised nutrition and health research while encouraging curiosity and positive attitudes toward science. Through interactive participation and discussions with facilitators, audiences gain a more approachable understanding of scientific research and its relevance to everyday life. Feedback from participants also supports the continuous improvement of the experience.

GEDI considerations: Accessibility and inclusion were central to the design of the escape room. The collaborative team format supports participation from people with different abilities and confidence levels, including neurodiverse audiences. Free public events and partnerships with programmes supporting underrepresented groups in STEM helped reduce financial and social barriers to participation.

Limitations found: The activity currently exists only as an in-person experience with limited participant capacity, restricting the number of people who can engage at one time. Additional limitations include English-only materials and the use of some consumable resources, which may affect accessibility, scalability, and environmental sustainability.

4.19 Science Nest

Title: Science Nest

Contributor: Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: <https://museuciencies.cat/es/el-nat/las-sedes/museo-de-ciencias-naturales-de-barcelona/nido-de-ciencia/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Science Museums and Festivals

Main objective: To foster curiosity and scientific thinking from early childhood by creating opportunities for children aged 0–6 to explore, observe, and investigate the natural world. The initiative aims to nurture an early interest in science through discovery-based learning and interaction with real natural objects and phenomena.

Summary of initiative: The Science Nest is a permanent space within the Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona dedicated to children aged 0–6 and their families. Through hands-on exploration of natural materials, specimens, sounds, images, and sensory stimuli, children are encouraged to ask questions, formulate hypotheses, and investigate their surroundings in a playful and self-directed way. The initiative also includes educational programmes for schools and early childhood educators.

Innovation factor: The initiative applies scientific inquiry methods to early childhood education, recognising children as active explorers and knowledge builders. Rather than providing predefined answers, it encourages open-ended investigation, experimentation, and dialogue between children and adults, helping to develop scientific thinking from a very young age.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The Science Nest promotes curiosity, observation skills, and critical thinking by allowing children to engage directly with natural materials and phenomena. It helps build confidence in asking questions, exploring possible explanations, and learning through investigation, while fostering positive attitudes towards science and discovery among both children and their caregivers.

GEDI considerations: The initiative is designed to be inclusive and accessible to all children during a key stage of development. By offering open-ended, sensory-based activities that do not require prior scientific knowledge, it enables participation regardless of background, learning style, language, or ability. The programme is also part of the museum's inclusion strategy, promoting equitable access to science learning opportunities from an early age.

Limitations found: N/A

4.20 Science SLAM

Title: Science SLAM

Contributor: ScienceSlam

Country of implementation: Germany

Start date of initiative: 2006

Website: <https://www.scienceslam.de/what-is-science-slam/#>

Target group: EDU, ACA,

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer, and Careers in R&I

Venues: Takes places in cultural centers, theaters or clubs, usually in the evening.

Main objective: The main objective of Science SLAM is to make science understandable, engaging, and socially relevant by challenging researchers to communicate their own work in creative and entertaining ways. The format encourages audiences to connect with complex scientific ideas while questioning how science influences society, culture, and everyday life.

Summary of initiative: Science SLAM is a live science communication event where researchers and students present their own research in short, 10-minute-talks, dynamic performances for a non-expert audience who gets to vote. Using storytelling, humour, visuals, experiments, and personal narratives, participants transform scientific presentations into interactive experiences where the audience actively responds, reflects, and often decides the winner.

Innovation factor: By blending academic research with creativity, emotion, and entertainment, Science SLAM breaks down traditional barriers between researchers and society, encouraging scientists to embrace vulnerability, accessibility, and provocative thinking when discussing complex or controversial topics.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Audiences gain exposure to current scientific research in a format that is accessible, memorable, and emotionally engaging. The initiative helps demystify science and researchers, fostering curiosity, trust, and critical reflection on scientific issues. Participants are encouraged not only to learn scientific facts, but also to engage more confidently with uncertainty, debate, and evidence-based thinking.

GEDI considerations: Science SLAM promotes inclusive science communication by valuing diverse voices, disciplines, communication styles, and lived experiences. Its informal and participatory format lowers barriers for audiences who may feel excluded from traditional academic environments, while offering visibility to early-career researchers and underrepresented groups in science.

Limitations found: N/A

4.21 Science Family Day/Open Day

Title: Science Family Day/Open Day

Contributor: Research Centers

Country of implementation: N/A

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, and Careers in R&I

Venues: Takes places in research centers/universities that open to the public.

Main objective: The main objective of the Family Day/Open Day is to bring research closer to society by creating accessible and engaging experiences for families and local communities. Through thematic activities related to the research center, the initiative aims to spark curiosity and encourage dialogue around complex global challenges.

Summary of initiative: The Family Day/Open Day is a participatory event hosted by a research centre that offers interactive activities for audiences of all ages, including science workshops, storytelling sessions, artistic activities, laboratory visits, and sustainability-themed experiences. The initiative creates opportunities for families to engage directly with researchers and explore how science connects to everyday life and societal issues.

Innovation factor: The project transforms the research centre into an open and interactive public space where science is experienced through creativity, participation, and informal learning.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a greater understanding of scientific research and sustainability-related issues while developing a more personal connection with science and researchers.

GEDI considerations: The initiative is designed to be inclusive and family-friendly, creating accessible entry points for people with different ages, cultural backgrounds, educational levels, and experiences with science.

Limitations found: N/A

4.22 Science Bingo

Title: Science Bingo

Contributor: N/A

Country of implementation: N/A

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil and Science in Summer

Venues: Takes places in non-formal spaces.

Main objective: The main objective of Science Bingo is to create an engaging and playful entry point to scientific concepts, encouraging participants to learn through interaction, curiosity, and active listening. The activity aims to reduce barriers to science engagement by transforming learning into a social, accessible, and enjoyable experience.

Summary of initiative: Science Bingo is an interactive science engagement game based on the traditional bingo format, where participants complete cards filled with scientific terms, concepts, discoveries, or questions.

Innovation factor: The project reimagines science learning through gamification, combining structured gameplay with informal science communication. By embedding scientific content into a familiar social game, it encourages active participation.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop a broader understanding of scientific ideas while engaging in a relaxed and collaborative environment. The format promotes curiosity, attention, and retention of information, while also encouraging positive attitudes toward science as something accessible, fun, and socially engaging.

GEDI considerations: Science Bingo supports inclusion by using a simple and familiar game structure that is accessible across ages, backgrounds, and levels of scientific knowledge.

Limitations found: N/A

4.23 Science Memory Game

Title: Science Memory Game (NASA Memory and Matching Games)

Contributor: NASA

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2000

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science in Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Takes place in non-formal spaces such as parks, science museums among others.

Main objective: The main objective of the Science Memory Game is to support informal learning of scientific concepts through play, strengthening memory, association, and curiosity. It aims to make science more approachable by turning knowledge acquisition into an active, engaging, and low-barrier experience.

Summary of initiative: Science Memory Game is a gamified science engagement activity inspired by the classic memory card game. Participants flip and match pairs of cards featuring scientific concepts, images, discoveries, or definitions.

Innovation factor: The project uses simple game mechanics to transform passive learning into active cognitive engagement. By linking visual, textual, and conceptual elements, it creates multiple pathways for understanding science, making ideas easier to retain through association, repetition, and play-based discovery.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants improve their recall and understanding of scientific concepts while developing positive associations with learning science.

GEDI considerations: The activity is highly inclusive due to its simplicity, low language demands, and flexible format, making it accessible across different ages, educational backgrounds, and abilities.

Limitations found: N/A

4.24 STEMcyclists

Title: STEMcyclists

Contributor: State University of New York at Buffalo

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: https://informalscience.org/project/stemcyclists-black-and-brown-youth-transforming-science-and-engineering-bikes/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities and Science In Summer

Venues: Informal learning spaces.

Main objective: The main objective of STEMcyclists is to engage Black and Brown youth in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) through bicycle repair, riding, and redesign activities. The project aims to strengthen STEM identity, promote engineering thinking, and connect scientific learning to participants' everyday environments and experiences.

Summary of initiative: STEMcyclists is a community-based informal STEM learning programme where young participants explore science and engineering through hands-on work with bicycles. Through summer institutes and group sessions, students learn biomechanics, engineering design, and problem-solving by rebuilding, customizing, and riding bikes while engaging with mentors, researchers, and local community organisations.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by using bicycles as a "transparent technology" through which young people can directly explore scientific and engineering systems.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop practical STEM skills, including engineering design, mechanics, and scientific observation, while also gaining confidence and a stronger sense of belonging in STEM fields. The project encourages curiosity, teamwork, and critical thinking, and helps participants see science and engineering as relevant, accessible, and connected to their own communities and identities.

GEDI considerations: STEMcyclists explicitly focuses on historically underrepresented Black and Brown youth in STEM, using culturally sustaining and community-based learning approaches to address structural inequities in science education.

Limitations found: N/A

4.25 SOILSCAPE

Title: SOILSCAPE

Contributor: Association Française pour l'Étude du Sol

Country of implementation: France, Portugal, Switzerland, Poland, Italy, Finland, Germany, and Bulgaria

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: <https://soilscape.eu/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities and Soil

Venues: SOILSCAPE takes place through distributed “Soils and Arts Orchestras,” festivals, workshops, schools, public spaces, cultural institutions, community settings, and online platforms across participating countries. Activities include soil festivals, artistic interventions, participatory science events, and creative educational programmes connecting science, art, and local communities.

Main objective: The main objective of SOILSCAPE is to increase soil literacy and public engagement with soil preservation by combining science, art, culture, and citizen participation. The initiative seeks to transform how society perceives soil, positioning it not only as a technical resource but as a living and cultural component essential for climate resilience, biodiversity, food systems, and human wellbeing.

Summary of initiative: SOILSCAPE is a large-scale European participatory initiative that uses artistic practices, storytelling, festivals, citizen engagement, and creative communication to reconnect people with soils. Through collaborations between scientists, artists, educators, cultural organisations, and citizens, the project develops innovative soil literacy activities, supports grassroots initiatives through open calls, and builds an international network dedicated to soil awareness and sustainable soil governance.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by merging soil science with artistic and cultural practices to address complex environmental challenges through emotional, sensory, and participatory experiences.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop a deeper understanding of soil ecosystems, sustainability, and the social dimensions of environmental degradation. The project encourages citizens to see soil as a shared cultural and ecological responsibility, fostering more environmentally conscious attitudes, stronger emotional connections with landscapes, and increased engagement in sustainable practices and community action.

GEDI considerations: SOILSCAPE promotes inclusive participation through multilingual, community-based, and cross-sector approaches that engage artists, schools, NGOs, citizens, and underrepresented groups in soil literacy activities. By valuing different forms of knowledge — scientific, artistic, local, and experiential — the project supports more equitable participation in environmental dialogue and broadens access to sustainability education and cultural engagement.

Limitations found: N/A

4.26 Women in Science Quiz

Title: Women in Science Quiz

Contributor: British Council

Country of implementation: UK

Start date of initiative: 2010

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: The activities can take place in schools, museums, science festivals, libraries, public events, universities, and online platforms.

Main objective: The main objective of a Women in Science Quiz is to increase public awareness of the contributions, achievements, and historical invisibility of women in science while challenging gender stereotypes associated with STEM careers. The activity seeks to promote more inclusive perceptions of scientific knowledge and scientific professions.

Summary of initiative: A Women in Science Quiz is an interactive educational activity where participants answer questions related to women scientists, scientific discoveries, gender bias in research, and inequalities in STEM fields.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in using gamification and participatory learning to address structural gender inequalities in science in an accessible and engaging way.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants improve their knowledge of women scientists and the social history of science while becoming more aware of gender biases and inequalities in STEM fields. The activity encourages critical reflection on stereotypes, promotes more inclusive attitudes toward scientific careers, and can inspire greater interest and confidence among girls and underrepresented groups in pursuing STEM pathways.

GEDI considerations: Gender equality is central to the initiative, as the activity explicitly seeks to increase the visibility of women and diverse role models in science.

Limitations found: N/A

4.27 Imagine Science Film Festival

Title: Imagine Science Film Festival

Contributor: Imagine Science Foundation

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2008

Website: <https://www.sciencenewwave.com/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: The festival takes place in cinemas, museums, universities, cultural centres, galleries, public spaces, and online platforms. Activities include film screenings, science cineforums, live discussions, immersive installations, workshops, performances, and encounters between filmmakers, scientists, artists, and audiences.

Main objective: The main objective of the festival is to engage the public with science through cinema and artistic storytelling, creating spaces where scientific ideas, ethical dilemmas, and societal challenges can be explored collectively through emotion, imagination, and critical dialogue.

Summary of initiative: Imagine Science Film Festival is an interdisciplinary science cineforum initiative that presents films, documentaries, animations, and experimental audiovisual works related to scientific themes such as neuroscience, ecology, artificial intelligence, biodiversity, health, climate change, and space exploration. Screenings are often accompanied by discussions with scientists, filmmakers, artists, and audiences, encouraging participatory reflection on the cultural and human dimensions of science.

Innovation factor: The festival innovates by positioning cinema not only as a tool for science communication but also as a creative and critical space for questioning how science shapes society and human experience.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop greater awareness of scientific topics and their ethical, social, and environmental implications while strengthening critical thinking and curiosity toward science.

GEDI considerations: Imagine Science Film Festival promotes diversity and inclusion by showcasing films and creators from varied cultural, disciplinary, and social backgrounds, including underrepresented voices in science and cinema. The

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

interdisciplinary and accessible format encourages participation from audiences beyond traditional scientific communities and supports more inclusive conversations around science, identity, ethics, and society.

Limitations found: N/A

4.28 Astronomy Outreach

Title: Astronomy Outreach

Contributor: N/A

Country of implementation: N/A

Start date of initiative: N/A

Website: https://iauoutreach.org/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: It includes “sidewalk astronomy” events where telescopes are installed in public urban spaces to allow spontaneous participation from passersby.

Main objective: The main objective of astronomical observation projects is to bring astronomy closer to society through direct observation of celestial phenomena and collective exploration of the night sky.

Summary of initiative: Astronomical observation activities invite participants to observe planets, the Moon, stars, galaxies, eclipses, or other celestial events using telescopes and guided interpretation by astronomers or educators.

Innovation factor: The innovation of these initiatives lies in transforming scientific observation into a shared social and sensory experience. Direct observation of the sky creates moments of wonder that challenge everyday perspectives and provoke reflection on scale, time, sustainability, and humanity’s relationship with the cosmos.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants improve their understanding of astronomy, space science, and scientific observation methods while developing curiosity, critical thinking, and appreciation for scientific exploration. Astronomical observations can also foster environmental awareness related to dark skies and light pollution, inspire interest in STEM careers, and strengthen collective experiences of discovery and dialogue across generations and communities.

GEDI considerations: N/A.

Limitations found: N/A

4.29 The Sound of Sciences (SoSTEAM)

Title: The Sound of Sciences (SoSTEAM)

Contributor: University of Bari Aldo Moro (UniBA)

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2019

Website: <https://sosteam.org/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Indoors or outdoors.

Main objective: The main objective is to translate scientific phenomena into musical and sonic experiences in order to make abstract scientific concepts more accessible, intuitive, and emotionally engaging.

Summary of initiative: The project transforms scientific data and concepts—such as cellular processes, physical laws, chemical structures, or environmental systems—into sound and music through sonification techniques. Participants may listen to or co-

create musical representations of scientific processes, explore how data “sounds,” and reflect on how auditory perception can reveal hidden patterns in science.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in using sound not as an illustration of science but as a direct representation of scientific data and processes. This creates a provocative shift in perception: science becomes something that can be heard, felt, and interpreted musically. It expands traditional science communication into sensory and creative domains, challenging the dominance of visual and textual explanations.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop alternative ways of understanding scientific concepts through auditory perception, improving engagement, curiosity, and memory retention.

GEDI considerations: These initiatives promote inclusion by relying on non-textual, sensory-based forms of communication that can be accessible to diverse audiences, including people with different educational backgrounds or learning styles.

Limitations found: N/A

4.30 Donner Pensant -Tasteful conversations to empower good practices in science

Title: Diner Pensant – Tasteful conversations to empower good practices in science”

Contributor: Integrity EU Project

Country of implementation: online

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: <https://h2020integrity.eu/toolkit/tools-researchers-supervisors/diner-pensant/>

Target group: ACA, EDU

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Careers in R&I

Venues: online

Main objective: The “Diner Pensant – Tasteful conversations to empower good practices in science” is a virtual workshop method to promote a food for thought critical reflection about good and bad scientific practices, in a relaxing, interactive, and enjoyable atmosphere, suitable for group sizes from 6 up to 300 guests.

Summary of initiative: During the event, guests are asked to reflect on their own experiences and practices, while discussing the cases presented, and to share views on how to promote and foster a culture of best scientific practices. The event is organised under the motto of a “dinner” event, where first there will be an Amuse for guests to get to know each other. Then, *Starters* will be served, where guests will be presented with three starters (cases) to choose and discuss one or the three. Four *Main Courses* (video-scenes) will be individually offered to guests to taste (watch) and share their opinions about them (food for thought discussion). And because “*dessert* goes to your heart and not to your belly”, the dinner finishes with a sweet moment to enjoy (inspiring thoughts to end)!

Innovation factor: Bring together Academics & Researchers that supervise students and future researchers, as well as institutional board members and integrity professionals, to an entertaining and inspiring virtual dinner experience.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Foster active contribution with thoughts and experiences by tasting special offers on integrity issues.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

4.31 Guerrilla Science

Title: Guerrilla Science

Contributor: CHROMDESIGN EU Doctoral Network

Country of implementation: Spain

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Start date of initiative: 2020

Website: <https://www.chromdesign.eu/blog/chromdesign-la-rambla-science-guerrilla/>

Target group: ACA, EDU, CIV

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Careers in R&I, Cities

Venues: city streets

Main objective: bringing scientists out of the lab to engage with citizens on the streets through impromptu, hand-drawn poster dynamics.

Summary of initiative: Guerilla Science is the result of an interactive, transdisciplinary science communication workshop. Researchers hit the pavement armed with blank signs and markers, inviting passersby to draw and write down questions they may have about DNA. The methodology was successfully adapted and expanded into the [PROTrEIN network](#), proving that transdisciplinary science engagement is highly scalable.

Innovation factor: The workshop bridges the gap between complex molecular biology and the general public by using experimental design and art as communication tools.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The activity can strengthen researchers' knowledge of informal, creative and street-based science communication methods and help them understand how to translate complex scientific content into concise, accessible and engaging messages. It can further contribute to shift attitudes by encouraging researchers to value direct public engagement beyond academic settings and increase openness to experimentation, creativity and dialogue with non-specialist audiences. For citizens, it can spark curiosity and awareness through unexpected encounters with science in public space.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

Picture 1: Guerrilla Science in action at Las Ramblas, Barcelona. (Ardila Photo Studio y Jonas Krebs).

D1.1 – 'Science4Everyone' Inspirational Formats

4.32 Sports and Science

Title: Sport and Science

Contributor: Associazione Festival della Scienza

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2009

Website: <https://sportech-tenero.ch/sport-e-scienza>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (i) dissemination

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities and Soil, Science In Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Palaces, parks, sport centres, everywhere

Main objective: Encourage people to understand that science is present in every movement we make: chemistry, physics, biology, mathematics, etc.

Summary of initiative: The format includes: workshops, exhibitions, special events and conferences on this subject under different points of view.

Innovation factor: There is innovation everyday in materials, equipment, instruments and technologies applied to sport and /or disabled people to be disseminated and known.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: People can easily learn by doing.

GEDI considerations: This initiative takes disability and gender perspectives into consideration

Limitations found: N/A

4.33 Science Reading Corner

Title: Science Reading Corner

Contributor: La Festa de la Ciència de Barcelona

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2012

Website: <https://www.barcelona.cat/festa-de-la-ciencia/es>

Target group: EDU, ACA, ENT, UND,

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: Science fairs, parks and libraries.

Main objective: To promote scientific literacy and curiosity by providing an accessible space where visitors can explore science-related content in an informal and self-directed way. The initiative aims to encourage lifelong learning and foster a greater interest in science among diverse audiences.

Summary of initiative: The Science Reading Corner is a quiet and welcoming space where visitors can browse and read science books, magazines, and popular science publications at their own pace. The initiative offers an informal learning environment that encourages exploration, reflection, and engagement with scientific topics in a relaxed setting.

Innovation factor: The initiative creates a dedicated space for science engagement through reading, offering an alternative to more interactive or presentation-based communication formats. By promoting self-guided discovery and learning, it enables visitors to engage with science according to their own interests and level of knowledge.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The Science Reading Corner increases access to scientific information and supports the development of scientific literacy. It encourages curiosity, broadens understanding of scientific topics, and fosters positive attitudes towards science by providing opportunities for independent exploration and learning.

GEDI considerations: The initiative supports inclusiveness by offering a flexible and accessible format that accommodates different learning styles, interests, and levels of scientific knowledge. The availability of diverse reading materials can reflect a variety of perspectives, disciplines, and societal issues, helping to engage a broad range of audiences and promote equitable access to science.

Limitations found: N/A

4.34 Mis/disinformation – A discussion game

Title: Mis/disinformation – A discussion game

Contributor: European Competence Centre for Science Communication

Country of implementation: Europe

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://scicommcentre.eu/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Health, Climate, Ocean, Cities and Soil

Venues: Various

Main objective: «Misinformation/Disinformation» is a discussion game (DG) developed to help participants to share their knowledge, experiences and opinions on facing the challenges and risks of the new communication ecosystem, in particular mis/disinformation.

Summary of initiative: DGs are playful activities to help people to share opinions and experiences on controversial and/or complex issues, from genetic testing to disinformation, from vaccines to privacy and AI. They help participants to understand better their opinions and opinions different from their own, and to form a deeper understanding on a particular issue and the constellation of stakes that involves. The «Misinformation/Disinformation» discussion game has been developed by the [COALESCE project](#) for the European Competence Centre for Science Communication to make people recognize and reflect on the various kinds of misinformation and disinformation, from totally fabricated to falsely contextualized true facts. It presents examples and asks people to share their own examples. The game needs to be played in small groups with the designated cards, for up to 40 people organised in groups of 4/5 people. Participants are also asked to choose and analyse case studies: who is spreading that news, why, what is the impact on who, what can be done to contrast the diffusion of this particular case of mis/disinformation. The game requires from 1,5 to 2 hours and has been used with different audiences: university students, researchers, journalists, science communicators. It can be used with secondary students of the last years, or general adult public. A second discussion game on “*Communicating science in times of crisis*”, similar in the format, has been developed to help participants to share their knowledge, experiences and opinions on communicating science during crises such as COVID-19, droughts, floods, fires, soil contaminations, etc. It is not suitable with the very young and/or general public, and it can be played with researchers and university students, journalists, science communicators, health workers, civil protection staff, civil society organizations and policy makers.

Innovation factor: People are seldom asked to express their opinions and to share their experiences in face to face encounters with strangers: discussion games present an alternative to the bubble effect of the social media, and promote the respectful, democratic discussion of complex and/or controversial issues

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Discussion games are participatory formats that empower participants to form and express their opinions and to feel that they can make the difference. They promote active citizenship.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

4.35 IUCAmundi: Connecting Research, Territory and Society

Title: IUCAmundi: Connecting Research, Territory and Society

Contributor: Aragonese Institute for Environmental Research (IUCA), University of Zaragoza (Spain)

Country of implementation: Spain - Worldwide

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://iuca.unizar.es/iucamundi/>

Target group: All

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Biodiversity, Environmental Sustainability, Territorial Resilience

Venues: IUCAmundi takes science beyond traditional venues into landscapes, protected natural areas, rural communities, urban spaces, cultural sites and locations where environmental and societal challenges are experienced firsthand. Activities are also hosted in research institutions, museums, cultural centres and community spaces, fostering dialogue between researchers, stakeholders and citizens.

Main objective: To connect research, territory and society through place-based science communication, enabling citizens, stakeholders and researchers to explore global challenges through local realities, foster dialogue, strengthen trust in science and encourage evidence-informed engagement with environmental and societal issues.

Summary of initiative: IUCAmundi is an innovative science communication and public engagement initiative developed by IUCA. The programme connects scientific research with society by taking citizens, researchers, territorial managers and local stakeholders to the places where environmental and societal challenges occur. Through guided field experiences, dialogue-based activities and place-based storytelling, participants explore topics such as climate change, biodiversity conservation, water management, sustainable development and territorial resilience. Rather than communicating science in conventional settings alone, IUCAmundi transforms landscapes, rural areas, urban environments and cultural sites into spaces for learning, reflection and participation. The initiative is designed to engage audiences that do not usually interact with scientific institutions by linking global challenges to local realities and everyday experiences. Scientific accuracy is ensured through the direct involvement of researchers and evidence-based content, while the participatory format promotes mutual learning between science and society. IUCAmundi strengthens public trust in science, fosters stakeholder collaboration and encourages citizens to become active participants in conversations about the future of their territories and communities.

Innovation factor: IUCAmundi innovates by moving science communication from conventional venues into the territories where environmental and societal challenges are experienced and addressed. Rather than relying on one-way dissemination, the format creates direct encounters between researchers, citizens, territorial managers, decision-makers and local communities, fostering dialogue and mutual learning. Its place-based approach allows participants to experience scientific evidence in real-world contexts, connecting global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss or water scarcity with tangible local realities. This makes complex scientific knowledge more accessible, relevant and memorable. The initiative also reaches audiences that do not typically engage with scientific institutions, including rural communities, land managers and local stakeholders. Scientific accuracy is ensured through the direct participation of researchers and evidence-based content, while the participatory design encourages reflection, discussion and collective problem-solving. By combining field experiences, storytelling, stakeholder engagement and interdisciplinary perspectives, IUCAmundi transforms landscapes into living spaces for science communication, strengthening trust in research and encouraging more informed public participation in societal and environmental decision-making.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: IUCAmundi increases participants' understanding of scientific research by connecting evidence-based knowledge with places, experiences and challenges that are directly relevant to their lives and communities. By interacting with researchers in real-world settings, participants gain a deeper understanding of environmental and societal issues and of how scientific knowledge contributes to addressing them. The initiative promotes more positive attitudes towards science by reducing the perceived distance between researchers and citizens, fostering trust, transparency and dialogue. Participants are encouraged to ask questions, share experiences and engage with scientific evidence in an accessible and meaningful way. IUCAmundi also supports behavioural change by encouraging participants to reflect on their own relationship with environmental and territorial challenges and on the role they can play in addressing them. The format

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

stimulates curiosity, critical thinking and informed engagement, while strengthening connections between scientific institutions, local stakeholders and communities. In addition, the initiative contributes to building long-term networks of collaboration and dialogue, creating opportunities for continued engagement with research, sustainability and evidence-informed decision-making processes.

GEDI considerations: GEDI considerations are integrated into the design and implementation of IUCAmundi. The initiative seeks to make scientific knowledge accessible to diverse audiences by reducing geographical, social and cultural barriers that often limit participation in science-related activities. Special attention is given to reaching audiences that are traditionally underrepresented in science communication, including rural communities, non-specialist publics, local stakeholders and groups with limited access to research institutions. Activities are designed to encourage participation, dialogue and knowledge exchange among people with different backgrounds, experiences and levels of scientific literacy. The initiative also promotes gender-sensitive and inclusive communication practices, ensuring diverse representation among researchers, experts and participants whenever possible. Scientific content is communicated using accessible language and participatory methodologies that value different forms of knowledge and experience. By bringing science into community spaces and territorial contexts, IUCAmundi contributes to more inclusive and equitable access to scientific knowledge while fostering a culture of participation, diversity and mutual respect. The format recognises that addressing complex societal and environmental challenges requires the involvement of multiple voices, perspectives and experiences.

Limitations found: One of the main challenges is ensuring that participation remains inclusive and accessible for all audiences. As many activities take place in outdoor or territorial settings, additional efforts are needed to improve accessibility for people with mobility, sensory or other participation barriers. Another limitation concerns scalability. The format relies heavily on direct interaction between researchers, stakeholders and participants, which is one of its greatest strengths but can also limit the number of people reached in each activity. Future developments could explore hybrid and digital participation models to broaden access while maintaining meaningful engagement. The initiative would also benefit from stronger mechanisms to collect long-term impact data and participant feedback, allowing a more systematic evaluation of changes in knowledge, attitudes and behaviours over time. Finally, further development of digital tools and online platforms could facilitate continued interaction between participants, researchers and local stakeholders beyond the activities themselves, helping to strengthen communities of practice and sustain engagement over the longer term.

5. Participatory and Citizen Science

5.1 BioBus

Title: BioBus

Contributor: BioBus Association

Country of implementation: USA

Start date of initiative: 2008

Website: <https://www.biobus.org/>

Target group: EDU, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, and Science In Summer.

Venues: A refurbished bus transformed into a mobile laboratory brings science directly to schools and communities.

Main objective: BioBus helps K–12 and college students discover, explore, and pursue science through hands-on learning experiences. By taking science directly to where people live, learn, and gather, its mobile laboratory makes scientific discovery accessible to diverse communities. BioBus is particularly committed to engaging students who have been historically underrepresented in science due to barriers related to race, gender, socioeconomic status, or physical access, helping create more equitable pathways into scientific learning and careers.

Summary of initiative: BioBus brings hands-on scientific learning directly to schools and communities through mobile laboratories built inside refurbished buses. Its mission is to help K–12 and college students discover, explore, and pursue science, with a particular focus on young people historically underrepresented in STEM. By connecting students with scientists and research-grade equipment in accessible community settings, BioBus promotes scientific curiosity, inclusion, and equitable access to science education.

Innovation factor: BioBus brings science closer to communities by transforming a refurbished vintage bus into a mobile laboratory that delivers hands-on scientific experiences directly to schools and community spaces. Guided by the vision that everyone should have the opportunity to reach their full scientific potential, BioBus has reached more than 400,000 students through collaborations with over 1,000 schools and community organizations since 2008.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: More than two-thirds of the schools served by BioBus are located in low-income communities. Recognized as an effective tool for expanding access to STEM education, BioBus promotes diversity by employing staff from groups underrepresented in science, providing students with relatable role models. Its impact is reflected in the high rate of teacher requests for return visits and in survey results showing increased student interest, confidence, and engagement in science.

GEDI considerations: Diversity and representation are central to the BioBus model: 80% of its staff come from groups historically underrepresented in STEM fields. This provides students—many of whom are Black, Hispanic, or female—with relatable role models and helps foster a stronger sense of belonging in science.

Limitations found: N/A

5.2 Sensetinta | Science Fanzine Workshop

Title: Sensetinta | Science Fanzine Workshop

Contributor: Citilab

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2012

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, and Science In Summer.

Venues: It takes place in community-based settings where people naturally meet, such as civic centres.

Main objective: To empower older adults (or other target groups such as students) through active participation in a community science magazine that fosters digital inclusion, lifelong learning, and engagement with scientific topics related to everyday interests such as food, the environment, or migration.

Summary of initiative: Sensetinta is a community-driven magazine created by older adults (or students) within a participatory learning environment. Through a learning by doing approach, participants explore scientific and societal topics connected to their lived experiences—such as nutrition, environmental change, and migration—while simultaneously developing digital skills. The magazine serves as both a learning tool and a platform for expression, enabling older adults to produce and share content using new technologies in a collaborative setting.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in combining science communication, digital literacy, and active ageing within a single co-creation process. Rather than positioning older adults as passive recipients of information, the initiative turns them into content creators who learn science and digital tools simultaneously. It also bridges science with personal and socially relevant topics, making scientific knowledge more meaningful and accessible through lived experience and community storytelling.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The initiative enhances participants' understanding of scientific and societal issues while strengthening their digital skills through active content creation. By engaging with topics that are relevant to their daily lives, participants develop greater confidence in using digital technologies, increase their interest in science, and adopt a more active role in accessing, interpreting, and sharing information. The collaborative process also fosters social participation, lifelong learning, and a sense of empowerment and belonging within the community.

GEDI considerations: The initiative actively promotes inclusion by targeting older adults, a group often underrepresented in digital and science communication spaces. It values diverse life experiences and ensures that all participants can contribute regardless of educational or technical background. The content selection supports intersectional perspectives, allowing for reflection on gender roles, cultural diversity, and social inequalities. The collaborative and accessible format helps reduce barriers linked to age, education level, and digital access, fostering equitable participation and intergenerational understanding.

Limitations found: N/A

5.3 GenB Educational board game

Title: GenB Educational Board Game (“BioRace”)

Contributor: APRE- Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: https://genb-project.eu/genb_toolkit/biorace/

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer and Careers in R&I

Venues: Pre-school and primary school settings in Rome, Italy

Main objective: To teach students, teachers, and families about the sustainable and circular bioeconomy through game-based learning.

Summary of initiative: BioRace is a learning tool designed to increase awareness of the bioeconomy and sustainable use of biological resources. Through questions, challenges, and collaborative activities, participants explore concepts related to circular systems, bio-based products, and environmental sustainability in an accessible and engaging way.

Innovation factor: The game was developed through a participatory co-design process involving students, teachers, scientists, educational experts, and science communicators. Multiple testing and validation phases, including workshops, focus groups, and

public school events, ensured scientific accuracy and educational relevance while actively involving children as contributors to the final product.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants improved their understanding of sustainable bioeconomy principles and developed greater awareness of resource conservation, circular production systems, and environmental sustainability through active and collaborative learning.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promoted inclusion by involving diverse participants in the co-creation process, avoiding gender stereotypes in content and visuals, and encouraging equal participation through collaborative gameplay. The game materials were also made available in multiple European languages to support cultural and linguistic accessibility.

Limitations found: Developing and validating an educational game required extensive coordination, expertise, and multiple testing phases to ensure educational quality, scientific accuracy, and accessibility for young audiences.

5.4 Ocean Science Jam

Title: Ocean Science Jam

Contributor: Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity, University of Oldenburg

Country of implementation: Germany

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: <https://hifmb.de/transfer/art-science/ocean-jam-night/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Ocean

Venues: street food/street bar venue in the centre of the city of Oldenburg

Main objective: If we think of science communication as creating moments in which science and society come into contact through a medium the questions I wanted to ask were, how can creative improvisation be used as this medium and what does this mean for how we create touching points with the ocean and ocean science.

Summary of initiative: Sharing complex oceanic research in an accessible way with the public is being identified by scientific institutions, universities, governmental departments, and NGOs as a critical intervention in promoting better engagement with the sea. Art–science collaborations play an integral role in this. The Ocean Science Jam brings musicians, artists, dancers, performers, and the public together to respond creatively in real time to visual and audio cues based on a theme related to marine scientists' work. By mixing creativity with science in an integrative way the Ocean Science Jam not only acts as a tool for public communication but also opens new ways for scientific data to be interpreted by non-scientists.

Innovation factor: The Ocean Science Jam brings together musicians, artists, dancers, performers, marine biodiversity scientists and the general public together to respond creatively in real time to visual and audio cues based on marine scientists' work. By creating an environment where everyone in the room jointly constructs the improvisational flow, regardless of their creative skills, a more democratic and expressive space is created for engagement with science and sharing with scientists.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: For scientists, they get to think about their work creatively and it is a platform to share ocean science with the public and to see, hear, and feel the public respond to their work. For the audience, it is an opportunity to learn and respond to Ocean science in a fun, interactive embodied and creative way.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: The format relies on people releasing their inhibitions and being willing to be vulnerable in a space and share, through creativity, their real-time responses to ocean science. On some evenings this is more difficult than others. Also, the format relies on having enthusiastic audiences who feel comfortable with awkward silences. This contributes to the jeopardy but also makes the event very exciting and unpredictable. The Ocean Science Jam has also proven that once the science is 'out there' you cannot control how the public reacts, and as such, we have had occasions with very surprising and conflicting reactions.

5.5 Engihack

Title: Engihack

Contributor: EIC

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: <https://engihack160.eic.cat/>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cancer, Cities, Soil and Careers in R&I

Venues: It needs a big space with tables and internet connection. It can be Science Museum Halls, Universities, among others.

Main objective: To engage engineering students in addressing major societal and technological challenges through collaborative problem-solving and innovation. The initiative aims to strengthen participants' capacity to develop practical solutions for issues such as energy, climate change, digital transformation, health, sustainable industry, and social equity.

Summary of initiative: Engihack is a 12-hour engineering hackathon that brings together students from engineering schools across Catalonia to work in teams on real-world challenges proposed by industry and society. Participants develop innovative solutions, receive guidance from mentors and professionals, and present their ideas to a jury at the end of the event. The hackathon serves as a meeting point between future engineers and leading companies and organizations.

Innovation factor: The initiative combines challenge-based learning, industry engagement, and collaborative innovation in an intensive and highly participatory format. By immersing students in real-world problems and encouraging multidisciplinary teamwork under time constraints, it creates an experiential learning environment that closely mirrors professional innovation processes.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Engihack enhances participants' understanding of complex societal challenges while strengthening skills such as teamwork, creativity, problem-solving, communication, and entrepreneurship. The experience encourages a proactive attitude towards innovation and reinforces the perception that engineers can play a key role in developing solutions for current and future societal needs.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promotes inclusive participation by bringing together students from different universities, backgrounds, and areas of engineering to work collaboratively on challenges with societal impact. The diversity of themes addressed—including health, climate action, digital transformation, and social equity—encourages participants to consider multiple perspectives and the broader social implications of technological solutions, supporting the principles of Gender Equality, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GEDI).

Limitations found: N/A

5.6 MULTI-ENGAGE Hackathon

Title: MULTI-ENGAGE Hackathon

Contributor: FISABIO and Valencia Innovation Capital

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://fisabio.san.gva.es/es/apoyo-a-la-investigacion/areas-de-gestion/unidad-de-ciencia-abierta/multi-engage/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer

Venues: Central venue with big space with tables and internet connection.

Main objective: The main objective of the MULTI-ENGAGE Hackathon is to foster multi-stakeholder participation in cancer research and innovation by involving citizens and other actors in the co-creation of solutions to major challenges in prevention,

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

diagnosis, treatment, and quality of life for cancer patients and survivors. The initiative aims to strengthen collaboration between science and society to generate more inclusive and impactful research outcomes.

Summary of initiative: MULTI-ENGAGE is a European project that organises a participatory hackathon where citizens, patients, researchers, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders work together in multidisciplinary teams. Participants use design thinking methodologies, mentoring, and collaborative sessions to develop innovative solutions to predefined cancer-related challenges aligned with the EU Cancer Mission.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by applying a multi-actor “multi-engagement” approach to cancer research, combining citizen science, co-creation, and hackathon methodologies within a biomedical context. It breaks traditional expert-only innovation models by positioning citizens and non-research stakeholders as active contributors in the ideation and problem-solving process, supported by structured mentoring and scientific guidance.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a deeper understanding of cancer-related challenges and research processes while developing practical innovation and collaboration skills. The experience strengthens awareness of prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and patient wellbeing issues, and encourages more active engagement with health innovation and evidence-based thinking. It also fosters empowerment and confidence in contributing to complex societal challenges.

GEDI considerations: MULTI-ENGAGE promotes inclusive participation by opening the hackathon to diverse profiles, including patients, caregivers, professionals, researchers, and citizens with no prior expertise.

Limitations found: N/A

5.7 Seed Library

Title: Seed Library

Contributor: Comune di Genova

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2027

Website: Not yet launched

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities and Soil

Venues: Local libraries, botanical garden

Main objective: Gather communities to exchange seeds and plants, celebrate biodiversity, and encourage active citizen engagement.

Summary of initiative: The seed library, aimed at fostering knowledge and environmental awareness through community engagement and accessible participatory practices, implies the conservation and circulation of seeds, to be borrowed as books and returned once the grown plants will produce new seeds.

Innovation factor: This format is innovative because it promotes intergenerational relationships and extends engagement to peri-urban areas.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The seed library initiative promotes environmental knowledge on local plants varieties and biodiversity, improving awareness on sustainable gardening and seasonal planting

GEDI considerations: It could be difficult to engage younger adults and teenagers.

Limitations found: Uneven participation due to low awareness.

5.8 Citizen Science Day

Title: Citizen Science Day

Contributor: Science Melting Pot and Aarhus Municipality

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Country of implementation: Denmark

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://projects.au.dk/citsci/fritidsforsker-for-en-dag-2023>

and Danish Science Festival <https://forsk.dk/kontakt-english/the-danish-science-festival>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): It depends on participating citizen science projects

Venues: Science Museums and local Libraries.

Main objective: Showing the public that they can participate in science through citizen science projects; allowing them to participate actively on the day in different types of projects to try it out, and ideally continue their engagement in those projects or others afterwards.

Summary of initiative: The 'Citizen Science Day' provides an opportunity for citizen science projects to showcase themselves to a large number of people (usual attendance 400-2000 people). Members of the public are encouraged to and shown how they can participate in the CS projects, aiming to motivate people to continue participation also after the event. It is thus an opportunity for CS projects to recruit new volunteers, and also to showcase to the public the wide range of options people have to get actively involved in and discuss science. Children are motivated by the provision of stickers when they interact with the different projects, and a large final "Fritidsforsker"-sticker when they visit at least 6 project stands.

Innovation factor: This was a new format for engaging the public with science in Denmark when it started in 2022. It is also used in a number of other countries, for example in relation to citizen science conferences.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Because there are a number of different types of citizen science projects participating focusing on very different things (e.g., biodiversity, freshwater, archaeology, history, AI, health, etc.), most people can find something they are interested in. This provides both a wide overview of and exposure to a lot of scientific themes as well as the possibility to dive deeper into a topic of their interest. Many discover new aspects of science and the world around them when they participate which may positively change their attitudes and behaviour.

GEDI considerations: The event is set up with short talks and demos and during a whole day, allowing anyone to participate as they are comfortable with.

Limitations found: Lack of resources (time and space) to organise the event, and for the CS projects to have time to participate.

5.9 Un giro di scienza - science cargo bike

Title: Un giro di scienza - science cargo bike

Contributor: Festival della Scienza

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: 2024

Website: This project was part of the Festival della Scienza <https://www.festivalscienza.it/>

Target group: ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: The activity is designed to take place in informal settings at unscheduled times. Public places frequented by citizens in city centres or on the outskirts: squares, parks, beaches.

Main objective: The idea of bringing a series of experiments and talks with researchers to busy public spaces in an unpredictable and unexpected way.

Summary of initiative: The project was launched in 2024 as part of an initiative aimed at tackling educational deprivation among a section of the population living in Genoa's historic centre. Since then, cargo bikes have been used in a variety of contexts, both during the Science Festival and at other city events.

Innovation factor: The innovative aspect of the initiative lies primarily in bringing scientific content to an unusual setting and surprising people with the presence of the bicycle and the events. The bicycle, being decorated with the logos of the Science Festival, is very eye-catching and immediately becomes a magnet for people.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: This type of activity makes it possible to convey a whole range of scientific topics in an entertaining and unexpected way, breaking with the tradition of having to visit a museum or a formal venue to learn about science

GEDI considerations: This type of activity makes it possible to convey a whole range of scientific topics in an entertaining and unexpected way, breaking with the tradition of having to visit a museum or a formal venue to learn about science

Limitations found: This type of activity makes it possible to convey a whole range of scientific topics in an entertaining and unexpected way, breaking with the tradition of having to visit a museum or a formal venue to learn about science.

5.10 Inspiraciència

Title: Inspiraciència

Contributor: CSIC

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2012

Website: <https://www.inspiraciencia.es/es>

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Science In Summer

Venues: It is based on an online platform. It includes libraries.

Main objective: To bring citizens closer to science through creative writing, encouraging participants to explore, interpret, and communicate scientific concepts through storytelling. The initiative aims to strengthen the connection between science and society by combining scientific inspiration with literary creativity.

Summary of initiative: Inspiraciencia is a science-inspired short story competition that invites young people and adults to write original narratives based on scientific themes. Through the creation and sharing of stories, participants engage with science in a creative and accessible way, fostering dialogue between science, literature, and society.

Innovation factor: The initiative innovatively uses creative writing as a science communication tool, moving beyond traditional dissemination formats. By encouraging participants to transform scientific ideas into fictional narratives, it promotes active engagement with science through imagination, creativity, and personal expression.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The competition enhances participants' understanding of scientific concepts while stimulating curiosity, creativity, and critical thinking. By actively involving citizens in the creation of science-inspired content, it fosters positive attitudes towards science and encourages greater interest in scientific topics and research.

GEDI considerations: The initiative promotes inclusiveness by being open to participants of different ages, backgrounds, and levels of scientific knowledge. Its combination of science and creative expression provides multiple entry points for engagement, helping to reach diverse audiences and supporting broader participation in science communication activities.

Limitations found: N/A

5.11 Community Gardens

Title: Community Gardens

Contributor: Orto Collettivo

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Country of implementation: Italy

Start date of initiative: Before 2010

Website: N/A

Target group: EDU, ACA, ENT, UND,

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cities, Soil and Science In Summer

Venues: Gardens

Main objective: The main objective of the Community Gardens project is to engage citizens in participatory science through hands-on gardening activities that promote environmental awareness, sustainability, and community involvement. The project aims to increase understanding of biodiversity, ecology, soil health, food systems, and climate-related challenges while fostering a sense of stewardship for local green spaces.

Summary of initiative: Community Gardens is a participatory science activity that brings people together to cultivate shared urban or local green spaces while learning about environmental and sustainability topics. Through practical gardening experiences, observation, data collection, and collaborative decision-making, participants explore ecological processes, sustainable food production, and the importance of biodiversity, strengthening both scientific literacy and community connections.

Innovation factor: The project innovatively combines citizen participation, environmental education, and experiential learning within community-managed green spaces. By integrating scientific concepts into everyday gardening practices, it creates an accessible and engaging pathway for participants to contribute to local sustainability efforts while generating knowledge through direct observation and shared learning.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain practical knowledge of ecological systems, sustainable gardening methods, and environmental challenges. The initiative encourages positive attitudes toward biodiversity conservation, climate action, and responsible resource use. Through active involvement, participants are more likely to adopt sustainable behaviours, such as reducing waste, supporting local food systems, and engaging in environmental stewardship within their communities.

GEDI considerations: The project is designed to be inclusive and accessible to people of different ages, genders, cultural backgrounds, abilities, and socioeconomic circumstances. Community gardens provide a welcoming environment where diverse participants can contribute their knowledge, experiences, and perspectives. Activities can be adapted to different needs, helping to reduce barriers to participation and ensuring equitable opportunities for learning, collaboration, and engagement with science and sustainability.

Limitations found: N/A

5.12 Ilustraciencia

Title: Ilustraciencia

Contributor: Ilustraciencia

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2009

Website: <https://ilustraciencia.info/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, UND,

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Ocean and Science In Summer

Venues: Science Museums

Main objective: The main objective of Ilustraciencia is to promote science communication through visual art, encouraging participants to translate scientific knowledge into accessible, accurate, and engaging illustrations. The project aims to foster curiosity and critical observation while highlighting the role of images in shaping how people understand complex scientific ideas.

Summary of initiative: Illustraciencia is an international science illustration competition that invites artists, researchers, students, and illustrators to create visual interpretations of scientific concepts, organisms, and natural phenomena. Through exhibitions, workshops, and public dissemination, the initiative connects art and science to make scientific knowledge more understandable and emotionally engaging for diverse audiences.

Innovation factor: The project combines scientific rigor with artistic creativity, positioning illustration as both a communication tool and a form of scientific interpretation. By encouraging participants to visually represent complex topics, Illustraciencia promotes new ways of observing, questioning, and communicating science.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants and audiences develop a deeper understanding of scientific subjects through visual storytelling and creative interpretation. The initiative encourages attention to detail, curiosity, and appreciation for the relationship between science, art, and observation.

GEDI considerations: Illustraciencia promotes inclusive participation by welcoming contributors from different disciplines, ages, cultures, and levels of scientific or artistic experience. The visual nature of the project creates accessible pathways for engagement across language and educational barriers, while the diversity of themes and perspectives helps represent multiple ways of understanding and communicating science.

Limitations found: N/A

5.13 Researchers-in-Residence

Title: Researchers-in-Residence

Contributor: Koninklijke Bibliotheek (KB) - National Library of the Netherlands

Country of implementation: Netherlands

Start date of initiative: 2014

Website: <https://lab.kb.nl/researcher-in-residence>

Target group: ACA, POL, ENT

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean and Cities and Soil

Venues: It happens within cultural, educational or community environments

Main objective: The main objective of Researchers-in-Residence is to bring scientific research into direct dialogue with society by embedding researchers within cultural, educational, or community environments. The initiative aims to humanise research, encourage public participation, and create spaces where scientific knowledge can be questioned, discussed, and connected to real-life experiences.

Summary of initiative: Researchers-in-Residence is a science engagement programme in which researchers temporarily work within non-academic settings such as museums, schools, cultural institutions, local organisations, or community spaces. Through workshops, conversations, collaborative activities, and public events, researchers share their work while engaging with local perspectives, concerns, and forms of knowledge. The residency format encourages two-way exchange rather than one-directional science communication.

Innovation factor: The project moves beyond traditional outreach by embedding researchers directly into community and cultural contexts.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a deeper and more personal understanding of research processes and contemporary scientific challenges. Direct interaction with researchers helps demystify science, build trust, and encourage critical engagement with scientific evidence and decision-making. The initiative also supports researchers in developing more inclusive, accessible, and socially responsive approaches to communication and public engagement

GEDI considerations: Researchers-in-Residence promotes inclusive participation by bringing science into accessible and community-based settings that reach audiences beyond traditional academic spaces.

Limitations found: N/A

5.14 Artist-in-Residence: ARTS AT CERN

Title: Artists-in-Residence: ARTS AT CERN

Contributor: CERN

Country of implementation: Switzerland

Start date of initiative: 2012

Website: https://arts.cern/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: ACA, POL, ENT

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer, Climate, Ocean, Cities and Soil

Venues: It happens within research centers

Main objective: The main objective of Artist-in-Residence programmes in research centres is to create meaningful exchanges between artistic practice and scientific research. By embedding artists within scientific environments, these initiatives encourage new ways of questioning, interpreting, and communicating complex scientific ideas, while fostering critical reflection on the social, ethical, and cultural dimensions of science.

Summary of initiative: Artist-in-Residence programmes invite artists to spend a period of time working alongside researchers within scientific institutions such as biomedical centres or physics laboratories.

Innovation factor: These programmes move beyond traditional science outreach by creating long-term, interdisciplinary collaborations between artists and scientists. Rather than simply illustrating scientific knowledge, artists are encouraged to challenge assumptions, explore uncertainty, and introduce emotional, philosophical, and sensory perspectives into scientific environments. This approach opens new ways of engaging with difficult or abstract topics such as genetics, artificial intelligence, climate change, or particle physics.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Audiences gain a more human and multidimensional understanding of science through artistic interpretation and public engagement activities. Residencies also influence researchers themselves by exposing them to alternative ways of thinking, observing, and communicating their work.

GEDI considerations: The combination of art and science creates multiple entry points for participation, helping to reach audiences who may feel excluded from traditional scientific spaces.

Limitations found: N/A

5.15 Bojos per la Ciència

Title: Bojos per la Ciència

Contributor: Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2013

Website: <https://www.fundaciocatalunya-lapedrera.com/ca/partir-del-15-setembre-inscripcions-obertes/cursos>

Target group: EDU

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Ocean, Cities, Soil, Science In Summer and Careers in R&I.

Venues: It happens in summer camps settings and/or research centers.

Main objective: The main objective of Bojos per la Ciència is to foster scientific vocations among high school students by giving them direct access to cutting-edge research environments and researchers. The programme aims to stimulate curiosity, critical thinking, and long-term engagement with science through immersive and hands-on experiences connected to real scientific challenges.

Summary of initiative: Bojos per la Ciència is an advanced educational programme in which students participate in thematic scientific courses hosted in leading research centres across Catalonia. Through laboratory practice, workshops, experiments, mentoring, and direct interaction with active researchers, participants explore disciplines such as biomedicine, artificial intelligence, physics, sustainability, mathematics, and bioengineering while experiencing the day-to-day reality of scientific research.

Innovation factor: The programme goes beyond traditional science camps by embedding young students within internationally recognised research institutions and exposing them to real scientific methodologies, technologies, and unresolved questions.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop scientific knowledge, laboratory skills, and a deeper understanding of how research contributes to society. The programme strengthens confidence, motivation, and interest in STEM careers while encouraging students to think independently, collaborate, and approach scientific uncertainty with curiosity and responsibility. It also helps students imagine themselves as future researchers and innovators.

GEDI considerations: Bojos per la Ciència promotes equal access to advanced scientific learning opportunities for motivated students from diverse backgrounds.

Limitations found: N/A

5.20 Science snorkeling

Title: Science snorkeling

Contributor: Anel·lides. Serveis ambientals marins.

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://anellides.com/event/esnorquels-bcn/>

Target group: EDU, ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Ocean and Science In Summer.

Venues: It happens in the Mediterranean Sea.

Main objective: The main objective is to connect citizens directly with the Mediterranean Sea through guided, safe underwater experiences. The activity aims to foster environmental awareness, curiosity, and critical reflection on urban marine ecosystems, helping participants understand biodiversity, human impact, and the need for ocean conservation through first-hand experience.

Summary of initiative: This initiative offers guided snorkeling experiences in Catalan beaches, led by marine biologists and environmental educators. Participants are equipped with full gear and accompanied during the immersion to observe and identify marine species, often contributing to citizen science platforms. The activity combines environmental education, scientific observation, and recreational immersion in real coastal ecosystems.

Innovation factor: The project transforms familiar urban beaches into accessible “living laboratories,” where participants literally enter the ecosystem they are learning about. By combining underwater immersion, scientific identification, and citizen science practices, it breaks the distance between people and marine environments.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain direct knowledge of marine species, habitats, and ecological interactions while developing a more emotional and embodied connection with the sea.

GEDI considerations: The programme promotes inclusion by offering structured, guided access to an activity that might otherwise feel technically or physically inaccessible. By providing equipment, supervision, and clear safety protocols, it lowers entry barriers for diverse participants with little or no prior experience.

Limitations found: N/A

5.21 Climate Stories Map (CSM)

Title: Climate Stories Map (CSM)

Contributor: VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel) as part of UP2030 project

Country of implementation: EU-wide (10 pilot cities)

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://m4d.services.iti.gr/up2030/app/test-city>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate

Venues: It includes an online platform

Main objective: The main objective of Climate Stories Map is to surface and understand how climate anxiety is experienced in everyday environments across European cities. By inviting community members to identify and map emotionally charged places, the project aims to connect environmental change with lived experience and stimulate reflection on the psychological and social dimensions of the climate crisis.

Summary of initiative: Climate Stories Map is a participatory mapping project in which community members from 10 pilot cities contribute to an interactive digital map by marking places that evoke feelings of climate anxiety. These locations might include coastal areas affected by erosion, industrial zones, wildfire-impacted landscapes, or urban spaces linked to heat stress or pollution. Each contribution can include personal reflections, creating a collective emotional geography of climate change that makes visible the lived realities of climate neutrality challenges.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining citizen science, emotional mapping, and climate communication. Instead of focusing only on physical data, it captures subjective and affective responses to environmental change, making invisible psychological impacts visible and shareable. As part of the UP2030 project, it reframes maps not just as spatial tools for urban planning, but as narratives of collective emotion, community voice, and environmental awareness.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop a more nuanced understanding of climate change by connecting scientific realities with personal and emotional experiences. The process can increase awareness of environmental risks, validate climate-related emotions, and encourage dialogue about coping strategies and collective action. It may also foster a stronger sense of environmental responsibility and community connection, while giving voice to perspectives often unnoticed in policy and planning.

GEDI considerations: The project promotes inclusion by valuing diverse emotional and lived experiences of climate change across different European cities, rather than privileging only expert or technical perspectives. The online platform ensures accessibility for participants from various educational, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds.

Limitations found: N/A

5.21 Thermo Staat

Title: Thermo Staat

Contributor: VPRO Medialab, Waag Futurelab, TU Delft, and the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences

Country of implementation: Netherlands

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: <https://thermo-staat.nl/about-thermo-staat>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate

Venues: Homes

Main objective: The main objective of Thermo-staat is to investigate heat stress in homes and its unequal impacts on people by involving citizens directly in data collection and interpretation. The project aims to increase awareness of indoor heat risks and empower residents with knowledge and tools to understand and act on their living conditions.

Summary of initiative: Thermo-staat is a citizen science project where residents across the Netherlands measure temperature and humidity in their homes using open-source sensors. These data are combined with scientific analysis and investigative

journalism, enabling participants to contribute to research, discuss findings with experts, and co-create public stories about heat stress and housing conditions.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining citizen science, journalism, and academic research into a single collaborative ecosystem. Citizens are not only data collectors but active research partners who help interpret results and shape narratives, turning environmental monitoring into a participatory and socially engaged investigation of climate inequality and urban living conditions.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain practical understanding of climate-related heat stress and its health implications, while also developing stronger awareness of inequalities in housing and urban environments. The process increases climate literacy, strengthens civic agency, and encourages people to advocate for better housing conditions and adaptation strategies.

GEDI considerations: Thermo-staat promotes inclusion by involving diverse households and prioritising those more vulnerable to heat stress, including people in lower-quality housing. By valuing lived experience as valid data, the project helps reduce barriers between experts and citizens and ensures that different social realities are represented in environmental research and decision-making.

Limitations found: N/A

5.22 Poseidon

Title: Poseidon

Contributor: Malta Chamber of Scientists, Blue EcoTech Ltd and Spark 15

Country of implementation: Malta

Start date of initiative: 2023

Website: <https://impetus4cs.eu/project-poseidon/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Ocean

Venues: Mediterranean Sea.

Main objective: The main objective of Project Poseidon is to protect and restore Mediterranean seagrass ecosystems (*Posidonia oceanica*) by engaging citizens in monitoring plastic pollution and supporting community-based conservation actions. The project also aims to empower diverse local actors to participate in environmental research and strengthen awareness of the ecological importance of marine habitats.

Summary of initiative: Project Poseidon is a citizen science initiative that brings together NGOs, researchers, refugees, and local communities to collect and analyse plastic pollution found in seagrass beach wrack along Mediterranean coasts. Participants take part in beach clean-ups, data collection, and public engagement activities, and also contribute to creative dissemination actions such as exhibitions and awareness campaigns about marine conservation.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining citizen science, social inclusion, and marine restoration in a single framework. It treats marginalised groups as active knowledge producers, integrates scientific data collection with artistic and public engagement activities, and links environmental monitoring with hands-on restoration efforts such as seagrass replanting, creating a holistic model of participatory marine conservation.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain direct understanding of marine ecosystems, plastic pollution dynamics, and the role of seagrass in coastal health. The hands-on and collaborative nature of the project strengthens environmental awareness, fosters a sense of stewardship for the sea, and encourages more sustainable behaviours and civic engagement in ocean conservation efforts.

GEDI considerations: Project Poseidon strongly promotes inclusion by actively involving refugees, local residents, and diverse community members in scientific and environmental activities.

Limitations found: N/A

5.23 Soil Sentinel

Title: Soil Sentinel

Contributor: the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF)

Country of implementation: Serbia

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://impetus4cs.eu/soil-sentinel/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities and Soil

Venues: Farms.

Main objective: To empower farmers to actively participate in soil health monitoring and safe, sustainable land management. The project aims to generate reliable, citizen-collected soil data to support evidence-based decisions on the use of sewage sludge in agriculture and to promote more circular and environmentally responsible farming systems.

Summary of initiative: Soil Sentinel is a citizen science initiative where farmers are trained to collect soil samples from their own fields following standardised protocols. These samples are analysed in collaboration with researchers and laboratories, alongside expert-collected controls, to assess soil quality and risks linked to sludge application. The project combines training, data collection, and policy engagement to build a community-driven soil monitoring network.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by transforming farmers into active data producers within a scientific monitoring system, rather than passive beneficiaries of agronomic advice. By combining citizen science, laboratory validation, and circular economy principles, it creates a low-cost, scalable model for soil monitoring that strengthens both scientific knowledge and local capacity for environmental decision-making.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain practical skills in soil sampling and a deeper understanding of soil health, contamination risks, and sustainable agricultural practices.

GEDI considerations: Soil Sentinel promotes inclusion by actively involving farming communities—often rural and underrepresented in research—as key contributors to scientific knowledge.

Limitations found: N/A

5.24 SENSORBIKES

Title: SENSORBIKES

Contributor: Futurium

Country of implementation: Germany

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: https://futurium.de/en/sensorbikes?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate

Venues: They build mobile sensors for their bikes and there is a platform where to visualize results.

Main objective: The main objective of SensorBikes is to empower citizens to actively participate in environmental monitoring and urban mobility research by transforming bicycles into mobile sensing stations. The project aims to generate open data on air quality, traffic conditions, and cycling safety while promoting more sustainable, healthy, and bike-friendly cities.

Summary of initiative: SensorBikes is a citizen science initiative developed by Futurium and re:edu in which participants build and install sensor kits on their bicycles to collect environmental and mobility-related data while cycling through the city. The sensors

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

measure variables such as air pollution, temperature, humidity, road quality, braking events, and overtaking distances by cars. The data are uploaded to open platforms and visualised collectively to support research, public discussion, and urban planning.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by combining DIY technology, open-source hardware, citizen science, and urban mobility into a participatory environmental sensing system. Instead of relying only on fixed monitoring stations, SensorBikes creates a distributed network of moving citizen-generated data, turning everyday cycling into a form of scientific observation and civic participation.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants develop practical skills in environmental sensing, data literacy, and urban analysis while gaining greater awareness of air pollution, traffic safety, and sustainable mobility challenges. The project encourages active citizenship, strengthens understanding of how data can influence urban policy, and promotes more environmentally conscious and participatory attitudes toward city life and transport.

GEDI considerations: SensorBikes promotes inclusive participation by enabling citizens with different backgrounds and expertise levels to contribute to scientific data collection and urban knowledge production.

Limitations found: N/A

5.25 Scientific Area Networks - SANs

Title: Scientific Area Networks - SANs

Contributor: DRESDEN-concept

Country of implementation: Germany

Start date of initiative: 2017

Website: <https://dresden-concept.de/scientific-area-networks/?lang=en>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Careers in R&I

Venues: Professional or informal spaces.

Main objective: The main objective of the Scientific Area Networks (SANs) is to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and dialogue among researchers, students, and other stakeholders across disciplines and sectors within the DRESDEN-concept alliance. It aims to strengthen scientific communities and create opportunities for new partnerships and interdisciplinary cooperation.

Summary of initiative: The Scientific Area Networks (SANs) are an ongoing science networking initiative developed by DRESDEN-concept, a strategic partnership of research institutions in Dresden. Participants from research, academia, and related fields come together in structured networking events where scientists present their research in short lectures (5 minutes, 5 slides). These presentations are followed by discussion sessions where working groups are formed to pursue joint goals, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and the creation of new collaborative links across all partner institutions.

Innovation factor: The innovation lies in its role as a catalyst for cross-disciplinary and cross-sector interaction, breaking down silos between research areas and professional communities within a large science alliance. By combining formal exchange (short lectures, pitches) with informal dialogue and working group formation, it creates flexible spaces where unexpected collaborations and ideas can emerge, strengthening the entire DRESDEN-concept ecosystem.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain broader awareness of ongoing research and innovation across fields within the alliance, while developing stronger professional networks and collaborative skills. The initiative encourages openness to interdisciplinary approaches, enhances communication between sectors, and can lead to new joint projects, shared methodologies, and increased engagement within the scientific community.

GEDI considerations: The Scientific Area Networks promote inclusion by ensuring diverse representation among speakers and participants across gender, career stages, disciplines, and institutional backgrounds within the DRESDEN-concept alliance.

Limitations found: N/A

5.26 European Researchers' Night

Title: European Researchers' Night

Contributor: European Commission

Country of implementation: EU

Start date of initiative: 2005

Website: <https://lanochedelosinvestigadores.es/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Careers in R&I

Venues: Diverse, city-dependent venues.

Main objective: The main objective of the European Researchers' Night is to bring researchers and society together in a shared space for dialogue, exchange, and mutual understanding. The event aims to showcase the diversity of research careers, foster curiosity about science, and strengthen public trust and engagement with research and innovation.

Summary of initiative: The main objective of the European Researchers' Night is to bring researchers and society together in a shared space for dialogue, exchange, and mutual understanding. The event aims to showcase the diversity of research careers, foster curiosity about science, and strengthen public trust and engagement with research and innovation.

Innovation factor: The initiative innovates by transforming researchers into active communicators in informal, public-facing environments, breaking down barriers between science and society. By combining entertainment, education, and direct interaction, it creates an open space where science is experienced as dynamic, relatable, and socially relevant, rather than confined to academic settings.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a better understanding of current research and the people behind it, while developing a more positive and approachable perception of science. The event encourages curiosity, inspires interest in scientific careers, and promotes critical thinking and dialogue about the role of research in addressing societal challenges.

GEDI considerations: The European Researchers' Night promotes inclusion by ensuring broad access to scientific knowledge across age groups, educational backgrounds, and communities. It highlights diverse researchers and career paths, helping to challenge stereotypes about who can be a scientist.

Limitations found: N/A

5.27 SOILTRIBES

Title: SOILTRIBES

Contributor: Horizon Europe project

Country of implementation: European

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://soiltribes.eu/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities and Soil

Venues: Activities take place across community spaces, cultural institutions, schools, festivals, workshops, exhibitions, public events, and online platforms throughout Europe. The project also develops "Soil Lab Activators," Stewardship Assemblies, soilathons, soilblitz events, and creative participatory activities connecting science, arts, and civic engagement.

Main objective: The main objective of SOILTRIBES is to foster soil literacy and reconnect society emotionally, culturally, and scientifically with soil as a living system essential for climate resilience, biodiversity, food security, and collective wellbeing. The project seeks to create new "back to Earth" narratives that inspire more sustainable relationships with land and ecosystems.

Summary of initiative: SOILTRIBES is a participatory European initiative that combines science, technology, arts, and citizen engagement to promote soil stewardship through creative and community-based approaches. The project supports grassroots initiatives, develops educational resources, organises large-scale public events, and builds networks of citizens, researchers, artists, and policymakers working together on soil awareness and regenerative practices.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by framing soil not only as an environmental issue but also as a cultural, emotional, and societal challenge. Through artistic practices, participatory events, and community-driven storytelling, SOILTRIBES explores provocative and experiential ways of understanding soil degradation and restoration, moving beyond traditional scientific communication toward collective behavioural and cultural transformation.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain deeper awareness of soil ecosystems and their role in climate adaptation, food systems, and environmental sustainability.

GEDI considerations: SOILTRIBES promotes inclusion through multi-actor participation involving citizens, artists, educators, researchers, grassroots organisations, and local communities from diverse social and cultural backgrounds.

Limitations found: N/A

5.27 FOTCIÈNCIA

Title: FOTCIÈNCIA

Contributor: FECYT & CSIC

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2003

Website: <https://fotciencia.es/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Ocean, Cities and Soil, Science In Summer

Venues: The project takes place through travelling exhibitions hosted in museums, cultural centres, universities, schools, libraries, and public institutions across Spain, as well as through online galleries, educational activities, and printed catalogues.

Main objective: The main objective of FOTCIÈNCIA is to bring science closer to society through photography, using visual language to reveal scientific phenomena, research processes, and hidden aspects of nature and technology. The initiative seeks to stimulate curiosity and critical observation while making science more accessible and emotionally engaging.

Summary of initiative: FOTCIÈNCIA is a science photography competition and travelling exhibition where participants submit images related to scientific concepts, natural phenomena, laboratory research, technology, or microscopic processes. The selected photographs are exhibited publicly alongside explanatory scientific texts, creating a dialogue between artistic creativity and scientific interpretation.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by transforming scientific observation into an artistic and narrative experience.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants and audiences develop greater interest in science and improved visual literacy regarding scientific phenomena and research processes.

GEDI considerations: FOTCIÈNCIA promotes inclusive participation by opening the competition to people from different ages, educational backgrounds, and professional sectors. The visual and non-specialised format lowers barriers to engagement with science and allows diverse perspectives, experiences, and forms of creativity to be represented within scientific communication and public exhibitions.

Limitations found: N/A

5.28 GEOVACUI

Title: GEOVACUI

Contributor: Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: <https://www.ucm.es/geovacui/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities

Venues: The project takes place through travelling exhibitions hosted in museums, cultural centres, universities, schools, libraries, and public institutions across Spain, as well as through online galleries, educational activities, and printed catalogues. Activities took place in villages, schools, local associations and public institutions. Results were shared through geovisors, story maps, documentaries, interviews, reports, and digital repositories available on the project website.

Main objective: The main objective of GEOVACUI is to generate knowledge about the causes and consequences of rural depopulation in inland Spain while identifying community initiatives and local strategies that help sustain population and improve quality of life in rural areas. The project seeks to support evidence-based public decision-making through participatory and geographically informed research.

Summary of initiative: GEOVACUI is a citizen science project that explores the social, economic, environmental, and infrastructural dimensions of rural depopulation through participatory research methods. By involving local inhabitants, students, associations, and institutions in interviews, data collection, and collaborative reflection, the project developed socio-economic and demographic geovisors, case-study guides, story maps, and recommendations for policymakers aimed at supporting rural resilience and territorial cohesion.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by applying citizen science methodologies to territorial and demographic challenges traditionally studied through top-down academic approaches. Through participatory mapping, digital visualisation tools, and collaborative knowledge production, GEOVACUI transforms rural inhabitants into active contributors to territorial research and policymaking.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a deeper understanding of the structural causes and impacts of rural depopulation while recognising the value of local knowledge and collective action in territorial development. It also contributes to changing perceptions of rural areas by highlighting both their challenges and opportunities.

GEDI considerations: GEOVACUI promotes inclusion by actively involving rural communities often underrepresented in research and policymaking processes.

Limitations found: N/A

5.29 Picaduras de conocimiento

Title: Picaduras de conocimiento

Contributor: Instituto Agroalimentario de Aragón (IA2) de la Universidad de Zaragoza

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2020

Website: <https://alimentandolaciencia.esciencia.es/picaduras-de-conocimiento/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cities and Soil

Venues: Activities took place in rural schools, natural environments, villages, protected areas, and community spaces across Aragón. The project also included field sampling activities, classroom sessions, public engagement events, and online dissemination through the project website and educational resources.

Main objective: The main objective of the project is to promote active citizen participation in scientific research related to ticks, fleas, and climate change, particularly among rural communities traditionally less connected to research institutions. The initiative

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

also seeks to improve scientific knowledge about the distribution of arthropods and their possible relationship with environmental and climate transformations.

Summary of initiative: Picaduras de conocimiento is a citizen science project that recruited and trained “arthropod hunters” to collect tick and flea samples across Aragón. Participants included rural school students, hunters, environmental protection agents, and local residents. Through training workshops, sampling kits, and collaborative research activities, citizens contributed to the collection and analysis of hundreds of arthropod samples used to study species distribution and potential climate-related changes.

Innovation factor: The project innovates by bringing scientific fieldwork and environmental monitoring directly into rural communities through participatory methodologies and hands-on laboratory materials. Rather than positioning citizens as passive audiences, the initiative integrates them into the research design and data collection process, combining science communication, environmental surveillance, and community engagement in a highly accessible and locally grounded format.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain practical understanding of biodiversity, vector ecology, climate change, and scientific research methods while developing stronger connections with environmental health issues affecting their own territories.

GEDI considerations: The project promotes inclusion by specifically targeting rural populations often underrepresented in citizen science initiatives and scientific outreach programmes.

Limitations found: N/A

5.30 Pavement Plants

Title: Pavement plants (original title: Stoepplantjes onderzoek)

Contributor: Hortus botanicus Leiden

Country of implementation: The Netherlands

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/hortus-botanicus/research-projects/pavement-plants-citizen-science-project>
<https://www.verspreidingsatlas.nl/projecten/floron/stoepplantjes/default.aspx>

Target group: EDU, CIV, ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cities, Soil, Science In Summer

Venues: homes, streets, and neighbourhoods

Main objective: The Pavement Plants Citizen Science Project invites citizens to monitor plant species growing around their homes, neighborhoods, or towns. The goal is to collaboratively monitor urban flora, measuring and revealing the species richness and biodiversity of the urban ecosystem, which can lead to new knowledge and insights for both citizens and the scientific community.

Summary of initiative: Carried out in the Netherlands as part of the European City of Science Leiden 2022 inviting citizens to observe, identify, and record the wild plants growing on and along sidewalks, pavements, and streets. It aims to investigate which plant species are able to grow in urban sidewalk environments, where they are found, and why they appear in particular locations. Participants are encouraged to go outside and look closely at the plants growing near their homes, streets, and neighbourhoods. Plants with visible leaves and flowers are usually the easiest to recognise. Citizens can then take a photo using their phone and identify the species by entering a plant name or uploading the image to the Pavements Plants platform. When a photo is uploaded, the system suggests the most likely plant species. Participants can verify the result using the project’s photo library or other reliable online resources. Once the plant has been identified, citizens can submit one or more observations through the platform, indicating which species they found and where.

Innovation factor: This project allows to foster a deeper interest in plants and to combat plant blindness, by investigating which pavement plants occur where and why, and how to raise awareness of plants, urban biodiversity, and the ecological value of everyday urban space using citizen science. By learning more about these plants, the ultimate goal is to contribute to the greening of villages and cities with wild plants.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The research questions focus on participants' motivations for engaging with the project, as well as their attitudes and knowledge about (pavement) plants.

GEDI considerations: The project has been designed with accessibility and inclusivity in mind. Participants of all ages are encouraged to take part, whether it's for a one-time observation or more frequent monitoring. During the course of the project, all collected monitoring data will be made available as open access for citizens to explore and analyze.

Limitations found: N/A

5.31 Genigma

Title: Genigma

Contributor: Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG)

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2021

Website: <https://citizenscience.eu/project/236>

Target group: EDU, CIV, ACA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer

Venues: online

Main objective: Genigma is a citizen science smartphone game that enables citizens to contribute to cancer research by analysing DNA fragments from widely used cancer cell lines. Its main goal is to help build reference genome maps that reveal cancer-related genomic alterations and interactions.

Summary of initiative: This innovative citizen science project invites the public to solve puzzle-based mobile games, which translates human intuition into real-world data for cancer research. Players shift, arrange, and align blocks representing small DNA fragments along a chromosome to achieve the highest possible score. By analyzing and rearranging DNA fragments of cancer cell lines, players actively help scientists map 3D genome structures to understand and combat cancer.

Innovation factor: Launched as part of the European Union's Horizon 2020 ORION Open Science project, Genigma stands out for its extreme participatory approach. Over two and a half years, more than 500 people—including cancer patients, high school students, and gamers—helped researchers to design the game to ensure it is both engaging and effective.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The map will make it possible to understand which parts of the genome of these cells play a fundamental role in the establishment and development of cancer, and will be very useful for designing more personalized and effective treatments against cancer.

GEDI considerations: Humans are remarkably better than traditional AI and algorithms at recognizing visual patterns. Solutions discovered by players are sent back to the lab, allowing scientists to test arrangements and map the reference genome much faster.

Limitations found: N/A

5.32 Citizen science journalism and Data4CitSciNews exhibition

Title: Citizen science journalism pairing and Data4CitSciNews exhibition

Contributor: Science for Change

Country of implementation: Portugal, Spain and Italy

Start date of initiative: 2022

Website: <https://newsera2020.eu/2023/03/01/citizen-science-in-the-news-data-stories-from-the-newsera-pilots/>
<https://newsera2020.eu/2022/12/09/data4citsci-news-exhibition/>

Target group: ACA, CIV, MEDIA

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): All

Venues: online, art galleries, science festivals

Main objective: Pair citizen scientists and journalists in order to co-create news articles or other engaging formats such as an art exhibition.

Summary of initiative: The data generated by citizen science projects can shed light on the state of local ecosystems or on pollution levels in a specific area: but can this data be also used by journalists to tell meaningful data stories, with and for local communities? In order to test the developing concept of Citizen Science Journalism and find ways to bring citizen science projects together with data journalists, NEWSERA project launched a pairing activity, involving journalists and citizen science projects, to work together to co-produce a data journalism article with data generated by the citizen science project. During the pairing activity, projects learned how a piece of journalism based on CS-generated data is born and conducted meetings with journalists to explore their dataset, define the focus of the article, and discuss the final results.

Innovation factor: This is the first time the concept of CS journalism was tested. Depending on the stage of the project, data collected and citizen scientists' involvement stories generated can be presented in a totally different manner, focusing on the process, direct sources involved, besides the scientific results. An associated exhibition featured interactive installations, co-creation processes and research methods that open a debate on how citizens and professionals in the journalistic world can come together to face current needs, especially in times of misinformation and fake news, and explore the potential of visual narratives, data journalism and the principles of quality scientific journalism.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Cooperating in the definition of the information needs of citizens and designing the collection of adequate datasets in a participatory and transparent manner can contribute to their use to promote change for the benefit of local communities and advocate for democracy.

GEDI considerations: Have in mind diversity of sources, considering intersectionality, and any ethical issues that may be raised.

Limitations found: The stage of the project and limited information can also be a handicap.

Credits: NEWSERA Project.

5.33 “Should our medicine go viral?” public tribunal-style debates

Title: “Should our medicine go viral?”

Contributor: ETH Zürich – ETHZ

Country of implementation: Switzerland

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/231102>

Target group: CIV, EDU, POL, ACA, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Cancer

Venues: theatres

Main objective: To inform, engage, and activate Swiss society in a balanced public debate on whether Switzerland should introduce measures to facilitate access to phage therapy as an alternative treatment for antibiotic-resistant infections.

Summary of initiative: “Should our medicine go viral?” is a science communication project that uses public tribunal-style debates in four Swiss cities to discuss access to phage therapy. During the tribunals, citizens, students, patients, clinicians, experts, policymakers, and other stakeholders will examine evidence, question experts, vote on key statements, and contribute to a wider reflection on the regulation of phage therapy in Switzerland.

Innovation factor: The project introduces the format of public “tribunals” as a novel approach to science communication, creating a structured, participatory space where complex biomedical and regulatory issues can be debated by diverse audiences. It also includes a strong evaluation framework to generate insights for science communication practice and research.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The project is expected to increase public understanding of antimicrobial resistance, phage therapy, and the regulatory challenges linked to access to innovative treatments. It aims to help participants form or reconsider their opinions on facilitated access to phage therapy, encourage informed civic debate, and provide stakeholders and policymakers with societal perspectives that may inform future discussions on health regulation.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

5.34 EMERGENCE@UPorto – Digital Media Science Communication Hackathon

Title: EMERGENCE@UPorto – Digital Media Science Communication Hackathon

Contributor: Universidade do Porto

Country of implementation: Portugal

Start date of initiative: 2021, 2022

Website: <https://www.up.pt/arquivoweb/tv.up.pt/videos/rccarzbp25fb.html?page=11&type=audio&view=grid>

<https://www.up.pt/casacomum/eventos/emergence-u-porto/>

Target group: ACA, EDU, Designers, visual artists

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): All

Venues: libraries, universities

Main objective: This initiative is a dedicated Digital Media Science Communication Hackathon designed to help researchers, artists, programmers, and communicators collaborate on sharing complex scientific concepts.

Summary of initiative: EMERGENCE@UPorto is structured in two phases: an initial training phase with lectures and practical exercises on digital science communication, followed by a project development phase organised as a sprint-based hackathon. During the process, participants work in interdisciplinary teams with professionals in art, programming, communication, and research, alongside highly qualified mentors to define a scientific or technological concept, select the communication format and

target audience, develop a work plan, and progressively build their collaborative projects while reporting daily on progress, challenges, and next steps. Innovative communication projects are presented in a public session on the last day of the event

Innovation factor: It offers an opportunity to deepen skills in science communication, by being challenged with new perspectives and expanding skills, such as using technologies like VR, film, and interactive media, participants are expected.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: The format can impact researchers by increasing their practical knowledge of evidence-based, engaging and target-centred science communication, while exposing them to digital tools, creative methods and interdisciplinary collaboration. It can help them see communication as an integral and strategic part of research, rather than an additional task, and by valuing the contribution of programmers, artists and creatives, and further encourage researchers to apply new communication approaches in their own work, develop more accessible and engaging outputs and collaborate beyond academia.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

5.35 The Journey: From Venice to Rotterdam

Title: The Journey: From Venice to Rotterdam

Contributor: Oceanographies Collective

Country of implementation: Italy, Spain, Morocco, Spain, Portugal, France, Belgium, Netherlands

Start date of initiative: 2025

Website: <https://oceanographiescollective.com/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (ii) dialogue and engagement

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Ocean

Venues: Port cities, ferries, fishermen boats, art spaces

Main objective: Systemic approaches to critical ocean literacy.

Summary of initiative: The aim is to create new connections and shared languages between institutions, human and non-human agents, so that our understanding of the ocean becomes more inclusive, ethical, and socially transformative. First-hand stories and lived experiences are interwoven with data and research to make knowledge tangible and affective. We believe that emotional connection is essential to creating new forms of imagination, care and responsibility toward the ocean.

Innovation factor: The Journey: From Venice to Rotterdam innovates ocean literacy by combining artistic practices, scientific research, and lived maritime experiences in mobile “living laboratories” across port cities and sea routes, creating emotionally engaging and participatory ways for communities to connect with ocean issues through direct collaboration with coastal actors and non-human perspectives.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Living Laboratories: We don't observe the sea from afar: we travel by water, work in maritime environments, and collaborate with coastal communities and maritime workers. Each project becomes a living laboratory and residency, where artists and scientists co-produce knowledge in community.

GEDI considerations: N/A

Limitations found: N/A

5.23 OdourCollect

Title: OdourCollect

Contributor: Science for Change

Country of implementation: Spain

Start date of initiative: 2018

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Website: <https://www.scienceforchange.eu/en/project/odourcollect/>

Target group: EDU, ACA, POL, ENT, UND

Public engagement level: (iii) participatory and citizen science

Topic relevance (aligned with the EU Missions or other): Climate, Cities and pollution, health

Venues: Streets.

Main objective: OdourCollect is a citizen science application that puts odour pollution issues on the map, empowering citizens affected by odour issues.

Summary of initiative: OdourCollect was created and piloted under the EU-funded D-NOSES project to address odour pollution as an under-recognised environmental and public health issue by empowering citizens to actively participate in its monitoring and governance, generating evidence to inform policies and reduce environmental injustice through participatory science and co-created solutions. OdourCollect has since been applied in multiple activities, with schools, museums, libraries, elder residencies, art & technology festivals or policy events not only to enable communities affected by odours to map and characterise bad smell events but also as a positive sensory tool related to individual and collective olfactory memories, for example from a particular neighborhood. The citizen-generated observations can be combined with stakeholder dialogues involving public authorities, industry, and researchers to identify sources of odour pollution and co-design mitigation strategies across multiple European and international case studies.

Innovation factor: OdourCollect shifts odour pollution management from a top-down, technical approach to a “quadruple helix” model that integrates citizens as active sensors and knowledge producers. It introduces real-time, geo-referenced perception data as a legitimate evidence base, bridging subjective sensory experience with environmental governance and policy development in a field traditionally lacking robust monitoring frameworks. The app, data platform, educational guides and other educational materials are available open access in Zenodo or other sources, such as CORDIS.

Impact on knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of the target audience: Participants gain a deeper understanding of environmental monitoring, pollution dynamics, and the social dimensions of environmental health. The process increases awareness of the legitimacy of lived experience as data, strengthens environmental agency, and encourages more active civic participation in local environmental decision-making. It also contributes to greater recognition of odour pollution as a real and impactful environmental issue.

GEDI considerations: Activities with OdourCollect have been inclusive-by design, including citizen participation by involving affected communities directly in the production of environmental knowledge, especially those often excluded from formal decision-making processes.

Limitations found: N/A

6. Other relevant sources

Hereby we provide a selection of repositories of successful and award-winning public engagement activities implemented in Science Festivals, European Researchers Night, Citizen Science Month, etc.

WHO compilation of innovative concepts to communicate science during the COVID-19 pandemic <https://www.who.int/teams/epi-win/scicom-compilation>

FECYT annual selection of innovative practices in promoting scientific culture and “Divulgateca” with results from projects funded under their yearly competitive funding call (in Spanish only).

<https://www.convocatoria.fecyt.es/publico/Catalogos/Catalogos.aspx>

<https://www.divulgateca.es/>

EUSEA - A database of tried and tested public engagement activities, created by engagement practitioners, for engagement practitioners, try something different for your next outreach activity.

<https://eusea.info/platform/>

IMPETUS funded Citizen Science projects and the European Union Prize for Citizen Science Awardees.

<https://impetus4cs.eu/accelerator-2025/#bootcamp-2025>

<https://ars.electronica.art/citizenscience/en/>

ERC Public Engagement with Research Awardees - <https://erc.europa.eu/manage-your-project/public-engagement-research-award>

Falling Walls Engage Finalists - Falling Walls Engage is the global platform for Science Engagement hosted by the Falling Walls Foundation and supported by the Hannover Re Foundation.

<https://falling-walls.com/engage>

V&A Public engagement projects

<https://vetenskapallmanhet.se/eng/projects/public-engagement-projects/>

Science gallery International network: Science Gallery is the world’s premier art-science network – igniting creativity and discovery where science and art collide.

<https://sciencegallery.org/>

SciArt was established in 2016, with the objective of triggering innovation in research by catalysing transdisciplinary collaboration between science, art and society. Hosted by the Joint Research Centre, the European Commission’s in-house science and knowledge service providing independent scientific advice to inform EU policy, JRC SciArt creates the space, the time, and the conditions for scientists, artists and policymakers to come together to exchange, investigate and co-create - with a shared drive to create insights and activities that can meaningfully influence our collective lives.

<https://science-art-society.ec.europa.eu/front>

SCIENCE COMES TO TOWN 2027

Consortium

@ScienceComesToTown

www.sciencecomestotown.eu

Funded by
the European Union

Bringing Science
Closer to Citizens